

SUPERSHINE

D5.4 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

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Technical references

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RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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4.0	05/12/2025	HE	Contribution to policy and regulatory parts
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Table of contents

Technical references.....	2
Table of contents	3
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1. Purpose of the Blueprint.....	7
1.2. Interdependencies with Other WPs and Tasks	8
1.3. How to use the Blueprint?	8
2. Setting the Stage for Social Housing in the Energy Transition...	10
3. Technology for Energy Transition in Social Housing	16
3.1. Justification of the Climate Analysis and Selection of Passive Strategies.....	16
3.1.1. Climate Files.....	16
3.1.2. Advantages of the Psychrometric Chart and the Givoni Bioclimatic Diagram	16
3.2. Passive Strategies by Climatic Context	17
3.2.1. Passive strategy analysis in the SUPERSHINE fellow cities	18
3.2.2. Passive strategies on Simulate data.....	19
4. Business Models for the Energy Transition in Social Housing	22
4.1 Funding Mechanisms for Social Housing Energy Projects.....	22
4.2 Public-Private Partnership (PPPs)	22
4.2.1. Guaranteed savings contract	22
4.2.2. Shared Savings contract	23
4.2.3. Energy Supply Contract.....	24
4.3 The Importance of Construction sector SME’s in the transition.....	25
5. LCA, LCC and S-LCIA	28
5.1 Role of LCA, LCC and SLCIA Assessments in Energy Transition Decision-Making.....	28
5.1.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).....	29
5.1.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment (S-LCIA)	30
5.1.3 Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	34
6. Social Acceptance	39
7. Follower City Analysis	41
7.1 Analysis for Setubal, Portugal	41
7.1.1 Technology for Energy Transition	41

7.1.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Portugal.....	42
7.1.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Portugal.....	45
7.1.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Portugal ..	51
7.2 Analysis for Zaragoza, Spain.....	52
7.2.1 Technology for Energy Transition	52
7.2.2. Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Spain.....	53
7.2.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Spain	56
7.2.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Spain	64
7.3 Analysis for Belgrade, Serbia.....	65
7.3.1 Technology for Energy Transition	65
7.3.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition in Serbia.....	66
7.3.3 LCA and S-LCIA for Serbia	69
7.3.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Serbia	71
7.4 Analysis for Kadıköy, Türkiye	72
7.4.1 Technology for Energy Transition.....	72
7.4.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Türkiye	73
7.4.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Türkiye	76
7.4.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in Türkiye.....	82
8. Replication Guidelines	84
8.1 Social Acceptance through Engagement.....	84
8.2 Environmental and Economic Performance: LCA- and LCC-informed Renovation Routes.....	88
8.3 Summary Guide on Policy, Finance and Organizational Capacity	92
8.3.1 Financial Mobilization and Blended Finance.....	92
8.3.2 Administrative and Technical Capacity	92
8.3.3 Regulatory and Enforcement Levers	93
8.3.4 RES and System Integration.....	93
9. Conclusion	95
References	98
ANNEX I Definitions of LCC Indicators.....	100

List of Tables

Table 1. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Portugal	11
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Table 2. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Spain	13
Table 3. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Serbia	13
Table 4. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Türkiye.....	14
Table 5: <i>List of Passive Strategies By Climatic Context</i>	20
Table 6. Guaranteed Savings ESCO Contract Structure	22
Table 7. Shared Savings ESCO Contract Structure	23
Table 8. Energy Supply Contract Structure.....	24
Table 9. Scale of the Analysis.....	31
Table 10. Indicators for Categories and Subcategories	32
Table 11. S-LCIA results of fellow cities.....	34
Table 12. Passive Strategies, Portugal	41
Table 13. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Portugal	41
Table 14. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Portugal	43
Table 15. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Portugal	44
Table 16. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Portugal	44
Table 17. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Portugal	45
Table 18. S-LCIA Results for Portugal	46
Table 19. General project information (Setúbal, Breijoiira)	47
Table 20. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory ((Setúbal-Breijoiira)).....	47
Table 21. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Setúbal, Breijoiira)	48
Table 22. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Setúbal, Breijoiira)	49
Table 23. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Setúbal, Breijoiira)	50
Table 24. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Setúbal, Breijoiira).....	51
Table 25. List of Passive Strategies, Spain.....	52
Table 26. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Spain.....	53
Table 27. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Spain	55
Table 28. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Spain	55
Table 29. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Spain	56
Table 30. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Spain	56
Table 31. S-LCIA Results for Spain	58
Table 32. General project information (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	59
Table 33. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	59
Table 34. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	60
Table 35. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	62
Table 36. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	63
Table 37. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	63
Table 38. List of Passive Strategies, Serbia	65
Table 39. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Serbia	65
Table 40. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Serbia	67
Table 41. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Serbia	68
Table 42. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Serbia.....	68

Table 43. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Serbia	69
Table 44. S-LCIA Results for Serbia	70
Table 45. List of Passive Strategies, Türkiye	72
Table 46. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Türkiye	72
Table 47. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Türkiye	74
Table 48. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Türkiye	74
Table 49. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Türkiye	75
Table 50. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Türkiye	75
Table 51. S-LCIA Results for Türkiye	77
Table 52. General project information (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	78
Table 53. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	78
Table 54. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	79
Table 55. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	80
Table 56. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	81
Table 57. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	82

List of Figures

Figure 1. Icons illustrating the passive strategies simulation process	18
Figure 2. Representation of capital expenditure (CAPEX) composition (Setúbal, Breijjoira)	48
Figure 3. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Setúbal, Breijjoira)	49
Figure 4. Breakdown of capital expenditure (CAPEX) by cost category (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	60
Figure 5. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)	61
Figure 6. Representation of capital expenditure (CAPEX) composition (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	79
Figure 7. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Istanbul – Kadiköy)	80

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Blueprint

The purpose of this document is to present the continued development and refinement of the Bottom-up Development and Fit of SUPERSHINE Blueprints, building upon the foundations established in Part 1¹. While the previous stage focused on defining the conceptual framework and identifying the “ready-to-go” solutions from the SUPERSHINE lighthouse districts, this second part advances the work by integrating the findings, analyses and co-creation outcomes emerging from the follower cities (FCs).

Drawing on the “ready-to-implement” projects from the lighthouse districts, it seeks to strengthen replication potential and create Blueprints that act as comprehensive guides for this transition. These Blueprints function as structured tools offering practical and adaptable strategies that combine technology, business models, lifecycle assessments (LCA, LCC, and SLCA), and co-creation approaches to enhance societal acceptance. Their purpose is to guarantee that proposed solutions are not only technically sound and environmentally sustainable, but also socially inclusive and economically practical.

By bringing together insights and methodologies from WP’s and Tasks and aligning them with the characteristics of the FCs, this deliverable provides a basis for developing practical and flexible strategies that can assist cities in addressing challenges of affordability, policy alignment, and community engagement. In doing so, it contributes to the overarching objectives of the SUPERSHINE project in fostering a more inclusive, sustainable, and context-sensitive transition to climate-neutral public, cooperative, and social housing.

In this context, it is pertinent to mention the European Affordable Housing Initiative, a collaboration of five key partners led by Housing Europe and co-funded by the EU, and the point for reference for EU’s first Affordable Housing Plan, a Just Renovation Wave and the New European Bauhaus. In its first phase (SHAPE EU 2022-2024), the initiative developed Blueprints for a just energy transition and supported 22 districts with mentorship, financial advice and capacity building². The initiative has now entered its second phase (SHAPE II 2024-26), which goes beyond retrofitting and energy efficiency, embracing broader values such as resilience, livability and circular economy principles. (<https://shape-affordablehousing.eu/>)

¹ SUPERSHINE Deliverable 5.3 “Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 1” 31 December 2024

² SHAPE EU Deliverable 4.1 “Blueprints for Replicating Lighthouse Districts, Guide for Municipalities, Housing Providers and Companies to create thriving affordable housing neighbourhoods “ 20 April 2024

1.2. Interdependencies with Other WPs and Tasks

The creation of the tailored SUPERSHINE Blueprints within this task draws on knowledge and outputs generated across multiple work packages and tasks in the project. The analysis of Fellow City bottom-up business models draws from the results of T3.1 under WP3, which examines and evaluates innovative business models relevant to public, cooperative, and social housing. Likewise, the evaluations covering technological interventions, life-cycle assessment (LCA), life-cycle costing (LCC), and social life-cycle assessment (SLCA) are informed by the outcomes of Task 3.3 and Task 4.2 and Task 3.5 which provide essential methodologies and data for evaluating environmental, technical, economic, and social impacts.

Insights from the KPI analysis conducted in Task 1.2 contributes directly to the Blueprint components related to all aspects of potential replication and scale up. These KPIs—focused particularly on engagement processes and social outcomes—will support the identification of the key conditions, drivers, mechanisms, and best practices that foster successful synergies for co-design, enabling policy climate and the baseline technical and financial frameworks.

1.3. How to use the Blueprint?

As housing is recognized as not merely a physical structure but a fundamental determinant of society's quality of life, influencing public health, education and economic opportunities. SUPERSHINE Blueprints developed in the project and summarized in this Deliverable, include underlining policy fundamentals as well as methodological insights based on evaluations in the project lighthouses to produce pathways for the Fellow Cities of SUPERSHINE. Policy configurations at both national and supra-national levels provide the foundations that shape the breadth of economic and technological interventions for affordable social housing in all countries. Policy choices also significantly determine financial options as resource allocations are policy outcomes. Technical interventions, though framed by geography and climatic conditions, are also impacted importantly by availability of funding for the technology choices. These two categories are separately treated for the Fellow Cities in the deliverable and constitute two essential components of the blueprint. LCA and SCLA analyses form critical components of any environmentally and socially just energy transition and are also included as separate categories.

The blueprints are designed to motivate stakeholders involved in planning or managing renovation projects to move beyond traditional decarbonisation approaches. They promote the integration of people-centred strategies with innovative building materials, services,

processes, and new business models. In particular, the blueprints serve as an inspiration for:

- ✓ **Housing providers** — including social, public, cooperative, and other organisations offering affordable housing.
- ✓ **Municipalities** — especially those engaged in providing social or affordable housing, social services, or working within planning and urban development departments.
- ✓ **Construction companies** — spanning renewable energy, digital solutions, electronics, and other technologies relevant to the housing sector.
- ✓ **Social Service Companies** — such as organisations offering social housing services and other community-based support services active in neighbourhoods, including incubators and entrepreneurship support structures.
- ✓ **National/Regional/Supra-regional Administrations** — with critical responsibilities in the formulation of supporting policies and regulations
- ✓ **Citizens and their organizations** — For bottom-up empowerment in social housing decision-making

2. Setting the Stage for Social Housing in the Energy Transition

The European Union's policy recommendations on social housing and energy efficiency are primarily focused on **tackling energy poverty** and ensuring a **socially just green transition** through comprehensive building renovation.

The key legislative instruments guiding these recommendations are the revised **Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)** and the **Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)**.

In order to pursue ambitions of energy gains, job creation, improve the living standards, in 2020 the Commission published the Renovation Wave Strategy along with an action plan and a document presenting available EU funding³. The Renovation Wave aims to renovate 35 million buildings by 2030, at least doubling the annual rate of energy renovations in the EU.

Investing in buildings can also inject a much-needed stimulus in the construction ecosystem and the broader economy. Renovation works are labour-intensive, create jobs and investments rooted in often local supply chains, can generate demand for highly energy and resource-efficient equipment and bring long-term value to properties. The objective is to at least double the annual energy renovation rate of residential and non-residential buildings by 2030 and to foster deep energy renovations. Mobilising forces at all levels towards these goals should result in 35 million building units renovated by 2030. The increased rate and depth of renovation will have to be maintained also post-2030, in order to reach EU-wide climate neutrality by 2050⁴.

Building renovation is one of the sectors facing the largest investment gap in the EU. The Commission estimates that in order to achieve the proposed 55% climate target by 2030, around EUR 275 billion of additional investments are needed per year.

When it comes to renovating residential buildings, there are major obstacles. People cannot find simple, attractive incentives for renovations. There are limited financing options, even if funding technically exists, there is lack of awareness, complex and confusing processes and regulatory constraints to for accessing public finance limit the use of these options. Despite similarities, large differences exist in the approaches to filling the gaps with regards to policy, finance and regulatory frameworks in different fellow cities. The inputs below give a resume

³ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/renovation-wave_en

⁴ "A Renovation Wave for Europe - greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives", Brussels, 14.10.2020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1603122220757&uri=CELEX:52020DC0662>

of the state-of-play and provides country specific proposals for the Fellow Cities of the SUPERSHINE project.

Portugal

Social housing in Portugal is mainly owned by municipalities which manage it directly or, especially in larger municipalities, through dedicated public companies. Furthermore, the Institute for Housing and Urban Rehabilitation (IHRU) also owns and manages its own social and affordable housing, providing a total 14,000 dwellings. IHRU is Portugal’s central housing body responsible for managing national housing programmes and urban rehabilitation initiatives. It collaborates with municipalities, cooperatives, and private actors to implement national housing policies. According to IHRU, based on data from the 2021 Census, public and not for profit entities own and manage altogether about 123,000 dwellings, or 2% of the total housing stock in the country.

Funding for social housing has significantly increased in recent years. Under the 1.º Direito Programme, financed through the PRR, Portugal aims to guarantee access to adequate housing for at least 26,000 vulnerable households by 2026. Beyond the PRR timeline, the national strategy “Construir Portugal” (2024–2030) foresees an investment of €4 billion for the construction of up to 59,000 new housing units by 2030, aiming to reinforce the public and affordable housing stock in a structural way. These households are identified as living in conditions of indignity (e.g., overcrowding, unsafe or inadequate structures) and lacking the financial capacity to resolve their situation on their own.

The Long-Term National Strategy to Combat Energy Poverty 2023-2050 defines energy poverty as „Inability to maintain housing with an adequate level of essential energy services, due to a combination of low income, low energy performance of housing, and energy costs.“ It is estimated that in Portugal, between 1.9 and 3 million people are in energy poverty, about 660,000 to 740,000 people in severe energy poverty, and between 1.2 and 2.3 million people in moderate energy poverty .

Portugal has clear, high-level targets (LTRS, NECP 2030) and ambitious goals for renovated area (748 million by 2050) and primary energy savings (34% by 2050), with a massive required investment (€110 billion for residential). The key pathway is mobilizing this capital and ensuring the social sector is prioritized.

Table 1. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Portugal

Stage	Focus Area	Proposed Actions and Targets
Phase 1: Mobilization (2024-2027)	De-risking and Scaling Finance	Target: Secure initial €15-20 billion through a mix of EU, EIB, and private funds. Action: Create a national "Social Housing Renovation Fund" (SHRF) utilizing guarantees to de-risk private bank lending for municipal and social housing renovations. Action: Implement a "One-Stop Shop" national

		<i>digital platform to manage applications, technical assistance, and certification for social housing complexes.</i>
<i>Phase 2: Deep Retrofit Implementation (2028-2035)</i>	<i>Industrializing and Skilling Up</i>	Target: Achieve 25% of the targeted residential renovated area. Action: Prioritize deep renovations (achieving NZEB or near-NZEB) in the highest-discomfort social housing units first (aligning with the goal of reducing discomfort hours). Action: Launch regional vocational training centers focused on "Green Building Trades" (insulation, heat pumps, smart controls) to meet labor demand.
<i>Phase 3: Integration and Replication (2036-2050)</i>	<i>Integrating RES and Replication</i>	Target: Achieve 100% of the LTRS goals and integrate on-site renewables. Action: Mandate and finance the installation of collective Renewable Energy Sources (RES) (e.g., solar PV, solar thermal) in all subsidized social housing retrofits. Action: Use public procurement to ensure long-term, fixed-price contracts for energy-efficient products to stabilize renovation costs.

Spain

Since the 1950s, Spain’s housing policy has strongly promoted homeownership, fostering a long-standing culture of property ownership. Social housing, mainly provided through the Vivienda de Protección Oficial (VPO) program, has historically prioritized affordable purchase over long-term rental, often allowing tenants to buy their homes at below-market prices, which has contributed to the country’s very small public social rental housing stock. Production of social housing for rent has actually increased over the past decade but it is often with an option to buy.

Besides this general description, it’s important to keep in mind that each autonomous community in Spain has its own regulation with regards to protected housing and the related funding schemes and rules. All these elements make it very hard to estimate the size of social housing sector in Spain, although data from AVS, the federation of public housing and land development agencies, show public companies manage roughly 318,000 dwellings. The vast majority of the public stock consists of multifamily buildings which require significant interventions in terms of energy efficiency and accessibility. Local housing agencies face barriers such as administrative constraints, complex funding rules, and ageing building stock requiring extensive work. Overall, both construction and renovation activities show positive momentum but remain insufficient to close Spain’s structural housing and energy performance gaps.

Spain's policy framework (ERESEE 2020, updated NECP, RRF) is well-aligned with EU directives, leveraging tax deductions and financial support to target 1,377,000 renovated dwellings. The pathway must focus on simplifying administrative hurdles and ensuring deep renovations are prioritized over shallow ones.

Table 2. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Spain

Stage	Focus Area	Proposed Actions and Targets
Phase 1: Catalyzation (2024-2027)	Administrative Simplification	Target: Achieve a 50% reduction in time for processing a social housing retrofit grant application. Action: Create a "Renovation Manager" (Gestor de Rehabilitación) national certification and subsidy program, focused specifically on supporting low-income and social housing communities (Comunidades de Propietarios) through the application and works process. Action: Increase the maximum tax deduction (60%) for projects that achieve deep retrofit.
Phase 2: Supply Chain Optimization (2028-2035)	Industrializing Solutions	Target: Increase the use of prefabricated, modular envelope and HVAC systems in multi-family social housing by 30% . Action: Fund research and pilot projects for industrialized deep renovation solutions for the common Spanish multi-family building archetypes. Action: Mandate energy performance standards for public housing providers to use a "Decarbonization Contract" approach, bundling deep retrofit and energy service provision.
Phase 3: Decarbonization and Data (2036-2050)	Smart Systems and Continuous Monitoring	Target: 100% of renovated social housing stock to be equipped with smart metering and monitoring. Action: Integrate energy performance data from renovated social housing into a national, public, anonymized database to allow for continuous policy refinement and verification of savings (linking to the EU's ERESEE reporting).

Serbia

Serbia has a massively privatized housing stock, with 87.3% being owner occupied, supplemented by a very small social rental (0.8%) and a somewhat bigger private rental (5.6%) sector. Local governments play an important role in ensuring adequate housing, particularly for the most vulnerable, and produce their own housing strategies. Major cities and municipalities have local housing agencies, which are set up as independent organisations and established at the discretion of local authorities.

Serbia's policy landscape (LEERUE 2021, LTRS, Low Carbon Strategy) is establishing the framework but faces challenges in execution across multiple ministries and the heavy reliance on inefficient solid-fuel boilers in single-family homes. The pathway needs to enforce mandatory maintenance/upgrades and drive fuel switching.

Table 3. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Serbia

Stage	Focus Area	Proposed Actions and Targets
Phase 1: Coordination and Enforcement (2024-2027)	Inter-Ministerial Action and Local Capacity	Target: Establish 100% compliance with the Law on Housing maintenance obligations in prioritized social housing zones. Action: Create a formal Inter-Ministerial Working Group (MoC-TI, MoME, Local Government) with shared budget and targets for thermal integrity improvements. Action: Pilot a "Boiler-to-Heat Pump/District Heating" mandatory subsidy

		<i>program for targeted neighborhoods to phase out old coal/wood boilers, linking air quality and energy goals.</i>
<i>Phase 2: Funding Mechanism Development (2028-2035)</i>	<i>Sustained Investment Mobilization</i>	Target: Launch a national Energy Efficiency Fund (EEF) capable of issuing concessional loans/grants for residential renovation, independent of annual state budget cycles. Action: Develop technical assistance/grants specifically for the renovation of multi-family buildings managed by the Local Self-Government Units , assisting with the required consensus among apartment owners.
<i>Phase 3: Deep Renovation Standardisation (2036-2050)</i>	<i>Zero-Emission Housing Focus</i>	Target: 75% of all state-subsidized renovations must achieve near-NZEB standards. Action: Introduce mandatory minimum insulation standards for all subsidized renovations and phase out all fossil-fuel based heating systems in new or deeply renovated social housing units.

Türkiye

In Türkiye, social housing provision and policy-making in this area are limited and focused on supporting access to home ownership. The main actor is TOKİ (Housing Development Administration of Türkiye), which operates as a subsidiary organization under the Ministry of Environment, Urbanism and Climate Change, and builds mass housing projects often through public-private partnerships. In addition to TOKİ, some local municipalities—primarily in İstanbul—also take part in housing provision, although their role is relatively small compared to TOKİ. The vast majority of housing in Türkiye is produced by private developers and the construction sector. A key driver of new housing supply in recent years is urban transformation/renewal projects which are focusing on replacing old, risky buildings with earthquake resilient new ones. However, the urban renewal projects are often criticized for displacement and gentrification.

Türkiye has the national ambition (Net-Zero 2053, NDC) and detailed roadmaps, but faces complexity due to the size of the stock, informality, and the critical need to align seismic safety upgrades with energy retrofits. The pathway must overcome these structural barriers at scale.

Table 4. Proposed Actions and Targets for Stages, Türkiye

Stage	Focus Area	Proposed Actions and Targets
<i>Phase 1: Integration and Standardisation (2024-2027)</i>	<i>Linking Safety and Energy</i>	Target: 100% of urban renewal projects must include mandatory NZEB-ready energy efficiency and RES components. Action: Create a unified "Dual Retrofit Grant/Loan" program that offers better financing terms for projects addressing both structural integrity (seismic) and energy performance (deep retrofit). Action: Formalize and expand city-level "Urban Transformation and Decarbonization Pilot" programs (e.g., İstanbul) into a national model with streamlined permitting and finance.

D5.4 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

<p><i>Phase 2: Capacity and Market Scale-Up (2028-2035)</i></p>	<p><i>Formalizing and Industrializing</i></p>	<p>Target: Formalize 75% of construction practices in high-growth urban areas through standardized, low-carbon building codes and inspections. Action: Incentivize the local manufacturing of high-quality insulation materials and prefabricated building systems to reduce costs and dependence on imports. Action: Establish a national Green Performance Certificate system linked to the building performance index to mobilize private investment through 'green mortgages' and property value premiums.</p>
<p><i>Phase 3: Net-Zero Mandates (2036-2050)</i></p>	<p><i>Mandates and Decarbonization</i></p>	<p>Target: Achieve the NDC and Net-Zero 2053 goals for the building sector. Action: Introduce a "Phase-Out Date" for inefficient, non-renovated social housing based on energy performance class (e.g., buildings below a certain class must be renovated or decommissioned by 2045).</p>

3. Technology for Energy Transition in Social Housing

The technical analysis of the potentials for a transition in the Fellow Cities is given below emulating the already available methods used in the project.

The data presented here were developed as a continuation of the work carried out in D5.3_Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities, Part 1. In that deliverable, the climatic conditions of the lighthouse cities were analysed using energy climate files. These files were introduced into the Givoni bioclimatic chart in order to identify passive solutions that could be applied to social housing within the context of the SUPERSHINE lighthouse cities. All data tables are included in the last annex, where the page layout was changed to horizontal instead of vertical, in order to make the data easier to read and visualise.

3.1. Justification of the Climate Analysis and Selection of Passive Strategies

3.1.1. Climate Files

The characterisation of each climatic context in the SUPERSHINE fellow cities was carried out using climate files in *.EPW* format. These files include hourly data on dry-bulb temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed, allowing the development of Givoni bioclimatic charts to be done directly and compared between cities. In this way, outdoor conditions can be related to indoor thermal comfort in a consistent manner.

3.1.2. Advantages of the Psychrometric Chart and the Givoni Bioclimatic Diagram

The Givoni bioclimatic chart combines temperature and humidity to define comfort zones, and includes parameters such as thermal mass, night ventilation, and building orientation, with the aim of identifying the most efficient passive measures.

This approach is applied because recent studies have shown that bioclimatic charts provide accurate recommendations in about 81% of cases, with even higher reliability in residential buildings, due to their lower internal loads.

A short timeline is included to help understand the evolution of these charts over the years, as well as their main applications (Herb et al, 2025).

- **1962 > Victor Olgyay_Origin Of Bioclimatic Charts.** The first bioclimatic chart was published by Victor Olgyay, combining temperature and relative humidity to define comfort zones and passive design strategies.
- **1969 > Baruch Givoni_First Publication.** Baruch Givoni developed his own bioclimatic chart, based on studies of thermal comfort and passive architecture. It was considered an innovation compared to Olgyay’s work because it focused on building design and analysed how the physical environment affects indoor conditions.
 - **1976 > Man, Climate And Architecture.** The chart was updated by Givoni to emphasise indoor comfort and bioclimatic strategies applied to architectural design.
 - **1978-1981 > Consolidation And Dissemination.** Additional factors such as solar radiation and wind were included, integrating a psychrometric approach and expanding its international use, especially in hot and humid climates.
 - **1992 > Update With Milne.** The chart was optimised for better visualisation and adapted to different climates (arid, tropical, temperate).
- **1998 > Urban Scale And New Approaches.** Givoni expanded the chart with extended ranges and introduced links between passive strategies, microclimate, and urban morphology, establishing it as a tool for both building and urban design.
- **2000-2010 > Digital Applications.** The chart was integrated into bioclimatic modelling and simulation software.
 - **2015 > Adaptive Models.** Comfort zones were updated considering occupants’ thermal responses and climate change scenarios.
 - **CURRENTLY > Urban Approaches.** The chart is used for studies on outdoor comfort, heat mitigation, and urban design, combining real-time climate data.

3.2. Passive Strategies by Climatic Context

**All data for this section are included in the final part of the chapter. A compilation of all these passive strategies is provided under the title “List of Passive Strategies by Climatic Context”*

A list of passive solutions for both cold and warm climate contexts has been provided, together with the description of two passive measures related to the retrofitting of existing buildings: The improvement of external insulation and the change of joinery in the existing buildings envelope.

The description of these passive strategies is based on the corresponding Givoni category, the passive constructive action required to achieve it, the technical principle that allows this

measure to work, the main objective of the strategy, and finally, specific examples of the constructive systems needed to apply it.

Figure 1. Icons illustrating the passive strategies simulation process

3.2.1. Passive strategy analysis in the SUPERSHINE fellow cities

**Each passive action that should be implemented in the SUPERSHINE Fellow Cities is included in the final part of the chapter. A compilation of all these data is provided under the title “List of Passive Strategies by SUPERSHINE Fellow Cities”*

The climatic files of the four fellow cities were incorporated into the Givoni bioclimatic chart in order to identify the most suitable passive design strategies for each lighthouse context. Three main groups of strategies were evaluated:

- **Heating passive strategies** included Thermal Mass, where solar heat is stored and released; Solar Gains, where solar radiation is captured through appropriate orientation and openings; and Thermal Insulation, where internal heat is conserved.
- **Retrofitting actions** are focused on fenestration replacement, where thermal performance and energy efficiency are improved through the use of high-performance glazing, and on the thermal envelope, where heat transfer is reduced and overall efficiency is increased by adding continuous insulation layers.

- **Cooling strategies** were defined as including cross ventilation, where warm air is removed and airflow is promoted; evaporative cooling, where air temperature is lowered through evaporation; mass cooling, where indoor temperature is stabilised by high thermal inertia; and solar protection, where overheating and glare are prevented.

3.2.2. Passive strategies on Simulate data

**All the final values about each SUPERSHINE fellow cities included in the final part of the chapter. A compilation of all these data is provided under the title “Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature”*

Understanding how the reduction in energy consumption is produced when each strategy is applied to a building, a 20 m² square model was used, exposed to the climate conditions of each city. The baseline was defined according to the constructive elements described by each municipality for its context.

The simulations developed take into account two main parameters: the reduction in energy demand, and the change in operative temperature (either a reduction or an increase) produced by each strategy.

In passive or low-energy buildings, an average operative temperature of 25 °C is considered the upper comfort limit; above this value, there may be a risk of overheating, so cooling strategies may be needed.

For this reason, 25 °C is used in these simulations as the threshold indicating the seasonal change between the winter period and the summer period.

- If Top > 25 °C → considered “summer / cooling dominant”
- If Top ≤ 25 °C → considered “winter / heating dominant”

Taking the previous context into account, it is stated that the months considered as summer or winter vary in each city and context, allowing a much more specific and detailed evaluation of each strategy.

As in the previous cases, the table with all simulated data is added in a horizontal format, so the reduction achieved by each strategy can be seen more clearly and easily, both in terms of energy consumption and operative temperature.

Table 5: List of Passive Strategies By Climatic Context

Winter Actions

GIVONI CATEGORY	PASSIVE ACTION	TECHNICAL SYSTEM	OBJECTIVE	EXAMPLES
ACTIVE SOLAR HEATING	Thermal mass	A massive wall or floor system is used (concrete, adobe...)	Solar heat is stored and released	Trombe wall
PASSIVE SOLAR HEATING	Solar Gains	Sunlight capture is maximised through building orientation and openings	Solar radiation is captured	Greenhouses or sunspaces
INTERNAL GAINS	Thermal Insulation	Internal heat produced by occupants and appliances is conserved	Internal heat is conserved	Double/triple glazing

Retrofitting Strategies

RETROFITTING STRATEGIES	PASSIVE ACTION	TECHNICAL SYSTEM	OBJECTIVE	EXAMPLES
INCREASE THE ENVELOPE	Replacement of joinery	Installation of high-performance glazing and airtight frames to reduce heat loss and infiltration	Thermal performance and energy efficiency are improved	Double/triple glazed windows
PASSIVE SOLAR HEATING	Building Envelope Retrofitting	Addition of continuous external or internal insulation layers on façades and roofs	Heat transfer is reduced and overall building efficiency is enhanced	ETICS/SATE systems

Summer Actions

GIVONI CATEGORY	PASSIVE ACTION	TECHNICAL SYSTEM	OBJECTIVE	EXAMPLES
NATURAL VENTILATION	Cross Ventilation	Opposing openings, courtyards	Warm air is removed and airflow is promoted	ventilation shafts
EVAPORATIVE COOLING	Evaporative Cooling + UTA	Adiabatic or water-based systems	Air temperature is lowered through evaporation	Evaporative panels, cooling ponds
MASS COOLING	Thermal Mass	Heavy walls or roofs with high thermal inertia	Indoor temperature is stabilised	massive roofs
SHADING DEVICES	Solar Protection	Systems that limit direct solar radiation while allowing daylight	Overheating and glare are prevented	Horizontal louvers, brise-soleil

4. Business Models for the Energy Transition in Social Housing

4.1 Funding Mechanisms for Social Housing Energy Projects

This section covers the essentials of national funding systems in the countries of each Fellow City and after providing basic information on financing types, builds decarbonization cost-benefit scenarios in Fellow City building stock. Also included in this chapter is a special section on the role of SME’s in the energy transition as a critical source of innovation, local employment and value added.

4.2 Public-Private Partnership (PPPs)

4.2.1. Guaranteed savings contract

Guaranteed-savings contract is proposed where the public owner seeks maximum budget certainty: the ESCO designs and maintains the measures and contractually guarantees a minimum annual energy saving, while the housing association finances the EE renovation project. Any out-performance is shared 80%/20% in favour of the ESCO, while under-performance triggers a compensatory payment to the housing company. The public partner therefore faces virtually no technical or credit risk but retains upside through a share of excess savings and 100% of the minimum guaranteed saving (cost of raising debt) and the capitalised uplift in property value and rent. Under this contract the parties involved are the ESCO and the social housing association. Below we describe the source of income, costs and expenses, responsibilities and risk allocation for each party under this contract.

Table 6. Guaranteed Savings ESCO Contract Structure

Guaranteed savings contract	Housing association	ESCO
Source of income	Energy savings from EE renovations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If energy saving is higher than the minimum guaranteed saving, the housing association receives minimum guaranteed 	Energy savings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If energy savings > minimum guaranteed savings, ESCO gets 80% of extra energy savings.

	<p>savings + 20% of extra energy savings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> otherwise receives the minimum guaranteed savings <p>Increased value of the building. Increased rent due to EE renovations.</p>	<p>otherwise pays the difference between the minimum guaranteed savings and actual energy savings.</p>
Costs	Investment cost	Maintenance and Operating costs of the EE renovations
Responsibilities	<p>Providing timely data for Annual Report (meter readings, Neogrid data, occupancy, major events).</p> <p>Granting the ESCO full access for supervision and inspection.</p>	<p>Acting as energy-performance advisor, construction supervisor, and savings guarantor.</p> <p>Supervising design & build to ensure energy measures are installed as intended</p>
Risk allocation	Not exposed to credit and technical risks	Technical risk and Credit risk

4.2.2. Shared Savings contract

Under the shared savings Contract, the ESCO is responsible for financing the EE renovations project, installing the EE renovations, and managing and maintaining the EE renovation systems. Under this contract the ESCO receives a minimum guaranteed savings (equal to cost of debt) + 65% of the extra energy savings, while the housing association receives 35% of the extra energy savings. Below we describe the source of income, costs and expenses, responsibilities and risk allocation for each party under this contract.

Table 7. Shared Savings ESCO Contract Structure

Shared contract	savings	Housing association	ESCO
Source of income		<p>Energy savings from EE renovations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If energy saving is higher than the minimum guaranteed saving, get 35% of extra energy savings. 	<p>Energy savings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> when energy savings > minimum guaranteed savings, gets minimum guaranteed savings +

	Increased value of the building. Increased in rent	65% of extra energy savings. otherwise, gets all energy savings.
Costs	The social housing association is not responsible for the maintenance and operation costs of the EE systems.	Maintenance and Operating costs of the EE renovations Investment cost
Responsibilities	Provide timely data for Annual Report (meter readings, Neogrid data, occupancy, major events). Grant the ESCO full access for supervision and inspection.	Acting as energy-performance advisor, construction supervisor, and savings guarantor. Arranges external financing. Supervising design & build to ensure energy measures are installed as intended
Risk allocation	Not exposed to credit and technical risks	Technical risk and Credit risk

4.2.3. Energy Supply Contract

Energy-supply contract (ESC) is suited to parcels that bundle energy generation with efficiency measures. The ESCO recovers its investment through an energy tariff that reflects the share $x\%$ of capex it pre-finances; the housing company pays the residual $(1 - x)\%$ and receives the corresponding share of savings. This structure is particularly advantageous when grant windows leave a funding gap higher than the ESCO's preferred exposure. The parties involved in this contract are: the ESCO and the social housing association. Below we describe the source of income, costs and expenses, responsibilities and risk allocation for each party under this contract.

Table 8. Energy Supply Contract Structure

ESC	Housing association	ESCO
Source of income	$(1-x)\%$ Energy savings from EE renovations, where $x\%$ represent how much of the investment cost is covered by the ESCO.	$x\%$ of Energy savings.

	Increased value of the building. Increased rent due to EE renovations.	
Costs	The social housing association is responsible for (1-X)% maintenance and operation costs of the EE systems. (1-X)% of investment cost	X% of Maintenance and Operating costs of the EE renovations X% of Investment cost
Responsibilities	Provide timely data for Annual Report (meter readings, Neogrid data, occupancy, major events). Grant the ESCO full access for supervision and inspection.	Acting as energy-performance advisor, construction supervisor, and savings guarantor. Arranges external financing. Supervising design & build to ensure energy measures are installed as intended
Risk allocation	a share of the credit risk	Technical risk and part of the credit risk

4.3 The Importance of Construction sector SME’s in the transition

Achieving Europe’s ambitious energy efficiency and climate goals will require a wave of green innovation, much of it driven by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). In sectors like building retrofits, renewable energy, and smart energy management, green innovative SMEs are developing technologies to reduce emissions and energy use. This is particularly relevant in the social housing context (for example, improving insulation, smart heating, or renewable integration in affordable housing) which is the focus of projects such as SUPERSHINE. In European countries including Italy, Denmark, Latvia, Spain, Portugal, Serbia, and Turkey, such SMEs play a pivotal role in the energy transition. SMEs have a unique potential to drive green innovation, thanks to their ability to innovate quickly, adapt to evolving market demands, and implement sustainable business models. This positions them to play a key role in accelerating progress toward net-zero goals and fostering a greener, more resilient global economy. However, to succeed and scale up their impact, these firms must navigate intellectual property rights (IPR), especially patents, to protect and commercialize their innovations. This deliverable explores SMEs’ potential in driving green innovation, examines the importance of IPR and patents for green innovative SMEs

in the energy efficiency sector, discusses current trends in “green patents,” identifies challenges SMEs face in using IPR, and suggests ways to support these enterprises. The insights are geared toward a broad audience – housing associations, policymakers, authorities, SMEs themselves, investors, and academics – highlighting how robust IPR strategies can accelerate green innovation for energy efficiency.

SMEs Unique Potential in Green Innovation

Small and medium-sized enterprises hold a unique and crucial potential for driving green innovation and contributing meaningfully to climate goals. Collectively responsible for a substantial carbon footprint, SMEs also stand out for their agility, motivation, and ability to adopt and scale environmental innovations faster than larger firms with entrenched business models (OECD 2024)⁵.

A significant share of SMEs – about one-third according to OECD data – are environmentally engaged, utilizing sustainable practices like solar energy, recycling, and improving energy efficiency (OECD 2024). These green SMEs tend to be more productive, pay higher wages, and experience faster salary growth than non-greening counterparts. Their motivation stems partly from cost reductions achieved through resource and input efficiency, but also from market-driven dynamics such as consumer willingness to pay a premium for sustainable products and pressure from large corporations demanding sustainable supply chains (OECD 2024).

In many regions, SMEs are integral not only to environmental sustainability but also to economic growth, as their green innovations open new markets and increase competitiveness. SMEs demonstrate particular strength in eco-innovation, eco-adoption, and eco-entrepreneurship. They are well-positioned to explore previously untapped “green” niches and product markets due to their small size and flexibility. Eco-innovative SMEs grow faster on average, and many start-ups embed sustainability in their core business operations from the outset (OECD 2019)⁶.

Green practices also translate into tangible cost savings for SMEs through improved process efficiency, product redesign, waste reduction, use of recycled materials, and energy-saving infrastructure. Evidence from various geographic contexts confirms that SMEs recognize and act on these financial incentives, with many reporting satisfaction with resource efficiency investments (OECD 2019).

Particularly relevant is the preponderance of SME’s in the construction sector. This is an important point related to local economical development, employment and value added. Across the EU, SMEs (firms with fewer than 250 employees) represent over 99% of all

⁵ https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/which-smes-are-greening_ddd00999-en.html

⁶ Koirala, S. (2019), “SMEs: Key drivers of green and inclusive growth”, OECD Green Growth Papers, No. 2019/03, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/8a51fc0c-en>.

enterprises, with micro and small firms accounting for the vast majority of that total; this general SME structure also applies to construction, where micro and small firms make up the bulk of business units and employment in the sector. In monetary terms, the construction of buildings sector generated about €177.9 billion in value added in 2022, and construction typically represents between 4–8% of GDP in many European countries, underlining its macroeconomic importance even though many firms are small-scale operators.

Securing intellectual property rights (IPR) plays a key role in enhancing SMEs ability to drive green innovation. IPR not only incentivizes green innovation but also supports SMEs in scaling their sustainable solutions by providing legal protections, enabling partnerships, and improving their market positioning.

5. LCA, LCC and S-LCIA

5.1 Role of LCA, LCC and S-LCIA Assessments in Energy Transition Decision-Making

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment (S-LCA) collectively provide a comprehensive framework to support energy transition decision-making within the SUPERSHINE initiative. By integrating environmental, economic, and social perspectives, the project ensures that proposed solutions for social housing are climate-neutral in the long term, financially viable, and socially acceptable for residents and local stakeholders.

SUPERSHINE analyses environmental and social environmental impacts in buildings and districts. It covers the policy, technical, environmental and social aspects of these projects, focusing on pilot implementations in Italy, Latvia, and Denmark as well as constructing pathways for the Fellow Cities of the Project by exploiting work done in the Lighthouse Cities. The following are the broad categories in which SUPERSHINE develops baselines and methods for analysis for both types of cities.

Technical Analysis; The lighthouse projects in Italy, Latvia, and Denmark have unique focus areas for their retrofit interventions. In Latvia, the emphasis is on historic buildings, considering climate impacts, heritage conservation, and occupant comfort. Italy focuses on public residential buildings, using materials derived from local agricultural waste, thereby promoting recycling and waste management. Denmark targets public housing with green renovations, aligning with its climate-neutral goals for 2050. The technical analysis evaluates the potential for energy savings, the effectiveness of various energy efficiency measures, and the application of sustainable technologies.

Economic Analysis; The main pillars of analyses carried out need to be complemented and in fact solidly based on the economic and financial analyses of the proposed solutions both with regards to specific buildings but also whole districts. This contribution naturally flows from the availability of finance for the transformations and carries the indelible mark of country attributes, despite most of the cities being in the EU. For the non-EU countries the projections become doubly important. The cost-benefit modelling of the required investments have been an important component also of the affordability argument of the Project and different types of funding mechanisms have been carefully dissected.

Environmental Analysis; focuses on the benefits of retrofit interventions in the pilot countries. It discusses the reduction in energy consumption and carbon emissions, the use of sustainable materials, and the potential for carbon credits. Waste management, particularly in Italy, where local agricultural waste is used in construction, is also highlighted. Despite

the substantial upfront costs, long-term benefits and potential funding from carbon credits make these interventions viable and sustainable.

The social impact analysis: examines the broader benefits of energy efficiency renovations. Improvements in accessibility, health, and comfort, job creation, and support for low-income citizens; benefits which are not easily monetised are discussed. Measures include enhanced indoor air quality, temperature control, and initiatives to support individuals with special needs. The analysis emphasises how these measures enhance the quality of life, stimulate economic activity, and promote social inclusion.

The methodologies to analyse of the lighthouse projects have given the opportunity for the fellow cities to provide an opportunity to evaluate the impact of their proposed interventions especially in buildings where socially, physically disadvantaged people live.

Deliverable D5.3 “Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to FCs – Part 1” introduced the conceptual role of these three methodologies and presented an initial environmental assessment focused on municipal waste management and wastewater treatment systems, as these offered the most reliable and comparable datasets across all pilot cities. In this Deliverable D5.4 – Part 2, the methodologies are further applied at building level in the follower cities, thereby linking the overarching strategic framework with concrete renovation scenarios.

5.1.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

The environmental, economic, and social indicators used in this second part are based on a structured data collection process led by each follower city. Through harmonized survey templates and locally developed technical reports, partners supplied key information including building geometry, surface areas, construction systems, energy consumption, and parcel characteristics.

These local inputs were combined with standardized environmental datasets, primarily ÖKOBAUDAT and other EN 15804+A2-compliant sources, to calculate performance indicators within a consistent methodological framework. Where detailed material specifications were not available, representative fallback values were applied to ensure comparability across case studies.

This hybrid approach guarantees that the results both reflect local conditions and remain methodologically robust for cross-country comparison, in line with the principles defined in Deliverables D3.4 “LCA and SLCA - Part 1” and D5.3 “Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to FCs – Part 1”.

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

The LCA in this Part 2 centers on emblematic social-housing initiatives in the follower cities, enhancing the city-level evaluation conducted in Part 1. The evaluation adopts a cradle-to-grave method, covering the extraction of raw materials, production, construction, usage, and final disposal phases. The functional unit is one m² of heated floor area (HFA) over a reference service life of 50 years.

The primary metric for comparison is the Global Warming Potential (GWP), represented in kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA and as the overall kg CO₂-eq for each project. Furthermore, a range of additional impact categories has been assessed:

- Ozone Depletion Potential – ODP,
- Acidification Potential – AP,
- Eutrophication Potential – EP,
- Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential – POCP,
- Abiotic Depletion Potential of fossil resources – ADP,
- Water Deprivation Potential – WDP, and
- Land Use Efficiency metric (the ratio of Gross Floor Area to plot area, GFA/parcel).

According to the methodological framework outlined in Deliverable D3.4 “LCA and SLCA - Part 1” and D5.3 “Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to FCs- Part 1”, the building LCAs incorporate:

- Standard background information sourced from recognized databases concerning materials and energy availability, and
- Inventories tailored to each project case study (geometry, construction methods, renovation strategies, and energy consumption profiles).

At this point in the data collection process, GWP stands as the most reliable indicator and is consequently utilized as the primary foundation for comparisons between countries. The other impact categories are viewed as supplementary indicators that will be improved as more specific local data on material makeup and energy mixes is obtained.

The relevant subsections under the analysis section (Chapter 7) provide a summary of the key LCA findings for each follower city.

5.1.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment (S-LCIA)

Increasingly relevant as a life cycle estimation tool and an addition to the traditional approaches, the S-LCIA has been used in SUPERSHINE for an evaluation of Fellow Cities implementations beyond the Project that have allowed consistent and comparable

evaluation across cities and interventions whose strong and weak aspects are explained in sections below. The SLCIA will be an integral part of any Blueprint and can be used by cities and municipalities beyond the Project.

5.1.2.1 Methodological Framework for the S-LCIA

In S-LCA, there are two main families of impact assessment (or Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment – S-LCIA approaches), the Reference Scale Approach (also known as Type I or Reference Scale S-LCIA) and the Impact Pathway Approach (also known as Type II or Impact Pathway S-LCIA), each responding to different practitioner aims.

To assess the magnitude and significance of the potential social impacts associated with the project, a **reference scale approach** is adopted. In this method, *performance reference points* represent predefined thresholds or targets that correspond to different levels of social performance or social risk. These reference points enable a consistent and comparable evaluation across cities and interventions, ensuring that both strengths and areas requiring improvement can be clearly identified.

The reference scale established for the project ranges from **-2 to +2**, where each level reflects a specific degree of compliance, effectiveness, and integration of social considerations:

Table 9. Scale of the Analysis

Scale Level	Description
2	Ideal performance. Best in class
1	Beyond compliance
0	Compliance with local and international laws and/or basic societal expectations
-1	Slightly below compliance level
-2	Starkly below compliance level

In line with the reference scale approach, the selection of social indicators and the definition of their corresponding value ranges were carried out through a multi-step and evidence-based process. At the beginning of the project, a comprehensive survey was designed and implemented in both lighthouse and follower cities. The questionnaire included technical, financial, environmental and social dimensions, providing a broad dataset to understand

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

existing practices, expectations and potential areas for improvement. The responses collected from the surveys enabled the identification of potential social indicators at both building and district levels.

Stakeholder subcategories and indicators used in the analysis are summarized in the table below. This version for the blueprint has become more inclusive with additional subcategories of “Knowledge and Capacity Development” and “Community Engagement”.

Table 10. Indicators for Categories and Subcategories

Indicators	Value Ranges
Tenants	
Accessibility (Building Level)	There are 4 questions in the survey answered by lighthouse cities. +2 is determined to “YES” answer to all questions which means the people in need are considered during the design phase. +1 is determined if 2 answers are “NO”, 0 if no improvement from the baseline phase. - degrees considered if there is no compliance with local rules
Health and comfort (Building Level)	There are 6 questions asked to lighthouses regarding if the tenants are able to control and monitor temperature, humidity, sunlight. +2 if “YES” to all questions, +1 if “No” to at least two questions in the category, 0 if compliance with local rules. -2 if no control over anything.
Inclusivity (District level)	+2 if women, ethnic minorities, young people and elders are taken into account, +1 if only some of two them are targeted, 0 if none targeted, -1 and -2 if any negative impacts to vulnerable groups
Safety (Building level)	There are 8 questions regarding safety in the survey. +2 to “YES” answers to at least 6 questions, +1 to “YES” answers to at least 4, 0 for basic safety measures, -1 and -2 for less or no safety measures.
Affordability (District level)	70-100% decrease in primary energy consumption is +2, 40-69% decrease in primary energy valued +1, less than 40% valued 0; if energy consumption increases it would be -1 and -2
Construction Company	
Health and safety (Implementation plan)	0 if compliance with national regulations applied
Risk assessment (Implementation plan)	+2 if risk assessment presented, 0 if known it is prepared, -2 if not prepared at all
Project Owner	
Compliance with regulations	0 if compliance with regulations applied

Indicators	Value Ranges
Quality assurance	+2 if comprehensive and actively monitored quality assurance plan, 0 if basic plan exists, -2 no plan leading to significant quality issues
Employee well-being and satisfaction	+2 if comprehensive programs and initiatives are in place to promote employee well-being and satisfaction with regular feedback and improvements, 0 if basic plans and regulations are applied, -2 if negative impacts on well-being, causing significant issues.
Stakeholder engagement	+2 if all key stakeholders are fully engaged with strong influence on decision making, 0 if minimal engagement stakeholders are informed but have little influence, -2 no engagement with stakeholders
Local Community	
Local employment (Building level)	+2 if expected to increase after the project, 0 just increased by the project and will go back to as usual, - 2 if there will be loss of jobs.
Economic development	+2 if any additional value created besides cost savings (raise in market value, job increase potential, etc.), 0 no additional value, -1 and -2 if there are any negative impacts.
Knowledge and Capacity Development	
Awareness	+2 if comprehensive and measurable improvements in awareness are demonstrated across stakeholders, 0 if compliance with basic legal and societal expectations, -2 if there is an absence of awareness programs or actions.
Capacity building activities	+2 if well-structured capacity building programs are implemented, 0 if basic requirements are met with standard training offerings, -2 if no capacity-building efforts, or activities result in a lack of knowledge or skills.
Changing attitudes	+2 if clear, positive shift in attitudes across most participants, with a strong commitment to change and the adoption of new behaviors, 0 if no significant change in attitudes, with participants maintaining their original views or behaviors, -2 if negative or regressive shift in attitudes, where participants become more resistant.
Community Engagement	
Level of engagement	+2 if high levels of participation with stakeholders showing active involvement in discussions and decision-making, 0 if only basic compliance is met with stakeholders being informed but not actively contributing, -2 if complete lack of engagement or active resistance to involvement in the activities.
Sense of belonging	+2 if a strong and positive connection where individuals actively identify with and engage in community activities, 0 if individuals recognize being part of the community but lack deeper emotional ties or active participation, -2 feelings of exclusion from the community.

The following table presents these aggregated scores for each follower city, showing their overall performance under the main social categories. Details will be explained under each city analysis in Chapter 7.

Table 11. S-LCIA results of fellow cities

	Zaragoza	Setubal	Kadıköy	Belgrade
<i>Tenants</i>	0.80	0.60	-0.40	0.20
<i>Construction Company</i>	0.50	0.00	-1.00	0.00
<i>Project Owner</i>	0.25	1.25	0.75	0.25
<i>Local Community</i>	0.50	0.50	-0.50	2.00
<i>Knowledge and Capacity Development</i>	0.67	0.33	0.00	1.00
<i>Community Engagement</i>	0.50	1.00	0.50	1.00

5.1.3 Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is applied within the SUPERSHINE project to assess the economic performance of renovation technologies implemented in residential buildings over their life cycle. In the context of social and affordable housing, where long-term cost efficiency and affordability are central concerns, LCC provides a structured approach to account for both upfront investment costs and costs incurred during building operation over a 50-year reference period.

The LCC analysis complements the energy performance assessment and the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) by providing the economic dimension of the evaluation. While energy analyses quantify reductions in energy demand and LCA addresses environmental impacts over the building life cycle, LCC translates technical performance into monetary terms, enabling an assessment of long-term economic implications. The alignment of time horizon and renovation scope across these methods ensures coherence between environmental and economic evaluations.

The main objective of the LCC analysis in SUPERSHINE is to characterise the life-cycle cost structure associated with the implemented renovation technologies and to quantify the economic effects related to reduced operational energy demand. The analysis supports the identification of renovation solutions that achieve a favourable balance between investment effort and long-term cost performance and that are suitable for replication across different European social-housing contexts.

5.1.3.1 Methodological Framework

The Life Cycle Costing analysis in SUPERSHINE follows a harmonised methodological framework to ensure consistency across pilot cases and alignment with the overall project approach. The analysis focuses on the economic implications of the renovation technologies implemented in the pilot buildings over a 50-year reference period.

Scope and System Boundaries

The LCC scope includes the main cost elements associated with the renovation measures and their operation during the analysis period. The system boundaries cover:

- Capital expenditure (CAPEX) related to renovation works, materials, equipment, and installation of technologies.
- Operational expenditure (OPEX) during the use phase, including energy consumption and routine operation.
- Replacement costs for components with service lives shorter than the analysis period.

End-of-life processes, such as demolition, disposal, or recycling of materials and components, are not included. Where relevant, residual values of components are considered at the end of the analysis period to reflect their remaining service life.

Cost Structure and Cost Elements

For each pilot case, the LCC analysis is structured around the identification and quantification of the main cost elements:

- Investment costs: disaggregated, where possible, by major renovation measures and technologies.
- Energy-related operational costs: derived from energy performance and corresponding energy prices.
- Maintenance and replacement costs: based on assumed technical lifetimes and standard maintenance practices.
- Residual values: where relevant, deducted from the cumulative costs at the end of the analysis period.

This structure allows the LCC results to transparently show how different technologies and measures contribute to total life-cycle costs and to the generation of operational cost savings over time, without implying a strict scenario-based comparison.

Consistency with Energy Performance and LCA

The LCC analysis is consistent with the energy performance assessment and the LCA in terms of reference period, renovation measures, and building characteristics. Energy consumption values used for calculating operational costs are derived from the same post-renovation energy simulations, ensuring coherence between technical and economic results.

5.1.3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The selection of economic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the LCC analysis in SUPERSHINE is guided by the need to provide a clear and transparent representation of life-cycle economic performance, while remaining consistent with data availability and methodological constraints across pilot cases. The adopted KPIs focus on aggregated and normalised cost indicators that can be robustly calculated for all pilots and that are commonly used in building-level LCC studies.

Together, these indicators allow the assessment of total life-cycle costs, their discounted and annualised values, and their distribution over time, without relying on complex scenario modelling or actor-specific cost allocations. The definition of these indicators can be found in Annex I.

5.1.3.3 General Assumptions

The LCC analysis carried out within the SUPERSHINE project is based on a harmonised set of assumptions to ensure consistency across pilot cases and alignment with the project's methodological framework.

The primary economic data used for the cost inventories were collected through structured surveys completed by project partners for each pilot case. These surveys provided information on investment costs and implemented renovation measures. However, for certain cost items, responses were incomplete or unavailable. In such cases, secondary data sources and standard reference values were used to complement the inventories and ensure completeness.

All costs are expressed using static prices, with no escalation or real price variation over time. Energy price inputs are based on average national energy prices for the year 2023 for each country involved in the project. This approach ensures comparability across pilots and avoids introducing additional uncertainty linked to long-term energy price projections.

The LCC analysis adopts a 50-year reference period, consistent with the reference service life used in the LCA and with typical assumptions for residential building renovation.

OPEX is calculated using a combination of measured energy consumption data and standardised cost assumptions. While energy consumption data were provided with a good level of accuracy for all pilots, detailed information on operation and maintenance costs was

not available in a consistent manner. Therefore, the following proxy values, expressed as percentages of total CAPEX, were applied uniformly across all pilot cases:

- Operation and maintenance costs: 1.5% of CAPEX per year
- Replacement and renewal costs: 0.7% of CAPEX per year
- Fixed recurring expenses: 0.8% of CAPEX per year

These values are in line with commonly adopted ranges in building life-cycle costing and asset management practice, where long-term non-energy costs are often estimated as a proportion of initial investment when project-specific data are not available.

A real discount rate of 4.5% is applied uniformly to all pilot cases. This value is consistent with European Commission recommendations for the economic appraisal of long-term public investments and supports comparability across countries and renovation contexts.

End-of-life processes, including demolition, disposal, or recycling of materials and components, are not included in the LCC scope. However, residual values of capital-intensive components are considered at the end of the analysis period, reflecting their remaining service life.

5.1.3.4 Limitations and Uncertainties

The LCC results presented in this chapter are subject to limitations arising from data availability and from the simplifying assumptions previously described. Although the primary economic inputs are based on project-specific data, the use of secondary sources to complete certain inventories may affect the precision of absolute cost values, particularly in cross-country comparisons.

The reliance on static prices and fixed 2023 energy price averages means that long-term changes in energy markets, taxation, or policy conditions are not captured. Operational cost indicators should therefore be interpreted as indicative of current conditions rather than as forecasts. Non-energy operational costs are estimated using standardised percentages of CAPEX. While this approach ensures consistency, it represents a simplified approximation of real operation, maintenance, and replacement patterns, which may vary across building typologies and local contexts. The application of a uniform discount rate across all pilot cases supports comparability but does not reflect country-specific financing conditions or risk profiles.

Finally, the exclusion of explicit end-of-life processes limits the ability of the analysis to capture future decommissioning or disposal effects. Residual values partially address this aspect but do not constitute a full end-of-life assessment. Overall, the results should be interpreted as a consistent and comparative economic assessment of the implemented renovation technologies, rather than as precise long-term cost forecasts.

Data Availability and Coverage of Pilot Cases

The LCC analysis presented in this chapter is based on the availability and quality of economic and operational data provided for each pilot case. While sufficient and consistent data were obtained for most pilots, this was not the case for all demonstration sites.

For two pilots: Zaragoza (ACTUR – Casona) and Belgrade (Block 29), the available information was insufficient to support a meaningful Life Cycle Costing analysis. In particular, the absence of reliable and complete data on investment costs, operational expenditures, and renovation-specific cost components prevented the calculation of LCC indicators and the derivation of robust economic insights.

As a result, these two pilots are not included in the quantitative LCC results and KPI-based analysis presented in relevant sections. Their exclusion is solely due to data limitations and does not reflect the technical relevance or strategic importance of the renovation concepts associated with these cases, which are addressed through other project assessments, including energy performance and environmental analyses.

The LCC results therefore focus on the pilot cases for which sufficient data were available to ensure methodological consistency, transparency, and robustness of the economic evaluation.

6. Social Acceptance

The SUPERSHINE “social acceptance through engagement” model, whose strategy has been explained in D1.2 - Engagement strategy and social acceptance KPIs, while its implementation in D1.3 and D1.4, Engagement for Social Housing refurbishment – Part 1 and Part 2, is an iterative, people-centred framework designed to embed residents as co-producers of deep energy-efficiency renovations. It combines structured dialogue, inclusive participation, transparent decision-making and continuous feedback loops, thereby linking technical renovation pathways with social ownership of outcomes. Replication of the model requires a phased approach that adapts to local vulnerabilities, governance maturity and community dynamics. Before going in detail of the blueprint, outlining the key phases, methods and critical replicability considerations, the following sections will present the current landscape of engagement and social acceptance in the four fellow cities, as well as a cross-country comparative analysis of their framework.

Across the four countries, several cross-cutting patterns emerge, considering that all districts exhibit, to different extents, a mismatch between the complexity of energy-efficiency renovation and the readiness of residents to engage with it, stemming from economic fragility, organisational fragmentation, limited literacy in energy and digital topics, or mistrust in institutions. A common tension exists between individual and collective benefits: homeowners frequently prioritise short-term personal gains or risk aversion over long-term, shared energy savings. Furthermore, the pace of renovation is constrained by structural conditions: in Portugal and Serbia by economic uncertainty, in Türkiye by seismic urgency, and in Spain by the need to coordinate multiple actors without losing momentum.

The enabling factors also show meaningful variation. Zaragoza offers the richest terrain for community-centred engagement, supported by long-standing social institutions. Portugal’s district has a more modest but culturally receptive environment where the right financial and informational frameworks can activate participation. Serbia’s New Belgrade possesses the strongest technical ecosystem but the weakest trust infrastructure, making engagement dependent on transparent governance and clear distribution of benefits. Kadıköy combines high institutional capacity with low community cohesion, implying that acceptance must be anchored in a reframing of energy efficiency as integral to seismic safety and long-term economic security.

Considered all together, these differences underscore the need for highly tailored engagement strategies stemming from the SUPERSHINE results, that acknowledge local histories, institutional maturity, socio-economic vulnerabilities and cultural priorities. While technical solutions may be transferable, social acceptance is not. The replication pathway success will depend on its ability to adapt its approach to the unique social topology of each district, building trust where it is lacking, strengthening participation where it is dormant, and

integrating energy efficiency into the everyday realities that shape how residents understand their homes, their safety and their future.

SUPERSHINE One Stop Shop goal is to offer a full renovation package with guaranteed energy savings to social housing residents and managers. The services will include;

- Coordinate existing market actors, including suppliers and innovative SMEs.
- Services to be offered to social housing managers and residents.
- Interaction with local businesses, innovative SMEs, and services to harmonize the Energy Efficient refurbishment at the district level.

The platform is functioning as a “**single-entry point**” managing the information flow between the governmental and business partners delivering the services and the potential customers.

7. Follower City Analysis

7.1 Analysis for Setubal, Portugal

7.1.1 Technology for Energy Transition

Based on the climatic analysis given in the Section 3.2.1, Setúbal shows a milder profile, where solar gains and thermal insulation are viewed as the most important heating actions, while cross ventilation and solar protection are recommended for summer.

Table 12. Passive Strategies, Portugal

HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS (1)		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation (2)	Evaporative Cooling system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection (3)
Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
	X	X	○	○	X			○

Table 13. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Portugal

		HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
		Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation	Evaporative system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection
		Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
Setúbal	Consumption reduction		-27%		-19%	-11%	-34%			-50%
	Operative temperature		+0.65°C		0.47°C	0.40°C	-1.72°C			-2.02°C

Setúbal has a temperate climate with dry and hot summers. One of the most effective passive heating strategies is to maximise solar gains in order to increase indoor temperature. As in the previous climate context (Zaragoza), the most effective way to reduce summer temperatures is the installation of solar shading elements.

For cities with similar climate characteristics, the blueprint should focus on:

Increasing winter solar captures and improving insulation envelope, while including **shading protection elements** on the façade and ensuring effective **cross-ventilation**.

7.1.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Portugal

The policy environment previously explained for Portugal is detailed for social housing enabling financial elements below;

- **Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR – RRF) – Components on housing & building renovation:** The RRP allocates hundreds of millions of euros to energy-efficiency renovations in residential buildings and to expanding/renovating affordable housing. Includes “Support Programme for Access to Housing” (Programa 1.º Direito) as an RRF-backed flagship investment (see below).
- **Programa 1.º Direito (Support Programme for Access to Housing) – RRF-funded project:** A nation-wide RRF project aiming to provide around 26,000 housing units via new construction, purchase or renovation with certified EE performance, focusing on vulnerable households and increasing public housing stock.
- **IFRRU 2020 & IFE2020 (Portugal 2020 financial instruments):** IFRRU 2020 (Instrumento Financeiro para a Reabilitação e Revitalização Urbanas) blends ERDF regional OPs with EIB/CEB and commercial banks to provide soft loans for urban rehabilitation, explicitly including building EE upgrades across all regions. IFE2020 – Financial Instrument for Energy, set up under Portugal 2020 to optimise leverage of public resources and boost investment in energy-efficiency actions, including in buildings.
- **EIB social/affordable housing loans:** “Social Housing Rehabilitation Programme PT”: EIB framework (approx. €1.5bn) for constructing/renovating ~5,000 social housing units with EE and climate-resilience criteria. EIB–Portugal €1.34bn affordable housing framework loan (2025) to build/renovate ~12,000 affordable rental units, aligned with EE standards and climate resilience.
- **Access to ELENA, EEEF & InvestEU:** Portuguese municipalities and IHRU/social-housing providers can tap ELENA for TA and eef / InvestEU-backed loans for large-scale renovation projects in public and social housing portfolios.
- **Programa 1.º Direito (national implementation):** National housing policy pillar since 2018 (~€700m budget), supporting renovation and rehabilitation of housing for disadvantaged households; municipalities/non-profits can renovate existing buildings and then rent them at affordable levels.
- **National Housing Programme (Programa Nacional de Habitação):** A broader multi-year framework which uses national and European funds (including PRR and Cohesion) to expand and renovate social/affordable housing, with energy-efficiency requirements embedded in the implementation by IHRU.

- **Support Programme for More Sustainable Buildings (Programa de Apoio a Edifícios Mais Sustentáveis “More Sustainable Buildings”):** National grant scheme (launched 2020, repeated in 2023–25) providing non-refundable subsidies (often 70–85% of costs) for building envelope improvements, efficient windows, HVAC replacement, RES and water-efficiency in residential buildings. Though primarily for private homeowners/condominiums, social-housing buildings can be eligible where the landlord authority applies.
- **Casa Eficiente 2020:** A government-backed loan/reimbursement programme offering up to 70% state reimbursement for equipment and works to make buildings more energy efficient, including insulation, glazing, and efficient systems.
- **Vale Eficiência (Efficiency Voucher) & E-Lar:** Efficiency Voucher (Vale Eficiência): vouchers targeted at energy-poor households to finance EE retrofits (insulation, windows, heating/cooling upgrades), implemented via accredited installers. E-Lar: scheme supporting acquisition of efficient appliances and electrification measures, especially for vulnerable families; complements renovation-oriented schemes.

The following is a modelling study of building stock investments cost/benefit analysis for Setubal.

7.1.3.1 Shared Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Setubal under the shared savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 57% and ROI of 8.25% for social housing and 6.94% to the ESCO.

Table 14. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Portugal

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	57.05%	8.25%	6.94%	4.23%
Wall	11	32.29%	6.48%	6.83%	3.50%
Roof	12	18.22%	4.27%	5.42%	2.58%
Floor	12	17.29%	3.92%	5.51%	2.31%
Window	18	8.24%	1.88%	3.05%	-0.65%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Setubal under the shared savings contract without taking into

account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 57% and ROI of 4.99% for social housing and 6.94% to the ESCO.

Table 15. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Portugal

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	57.05%	4.99%	6.94%	4.23%
Wall	15	32.29%	3.93%	6.83%	3.50%
Roof	16	18.22%	2.59%	5.42%	2.58%
Floor	16	17.29%	2.37%	5.51%	2.31%
Window	22	8.24%	1.14%	3.05%	-0.65%

7.1.3.2 Guaranteed Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Setubal under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 57% and ROI of 8.86% for social housing and 7.46% to the ESCO.

Table 16. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Portugal

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	57.05%	8.86%	7.46%	4.54%
Wall	11	32.29%	6.96%	7.34%	3.76%
Roof	12	18.22%	4.59%	5.82%	2.77%
Floor	12	17.29%	4.21%	5.92%	2.48%
Window	18	8.24%	2.02%	3.27%	0.70%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Sebutal under the shared savings contract without taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 57% and ROI of 5.36% for social housing and 7.46% to the ESCO.

Table 17. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Portugal

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	54.74%	5.36%	7.46%	4.54%
Wall	15	30.98%	4.22%	7.34%	3.76%
Roof	16	17.48%	2.78%	5.82%	2.77%
Floor	16	16.59%	2.55%	5.92%	2.48%
Window	22	7.90%	1.22%	3.27%	0.70%

7.1.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Portugal

7.1.3.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for Portugal

In Portugal, the representative example is Brejoeira in Setúbal, a collection of row houses experiencing partial energy upgrades. The structures feature a fairly lightweight envelope (concrete framework with uninsulated masonry walls), to which external thermal insulation (SATE/ETICS) is applied on specific façades, along with enhancements in roof insulation and building systems.

- GFA: 1,987 m²
- HFA: 1,950 m²
- Condition of renovation: Partial energy renovation based on ETICS on facades (6 cm EPS), roof improvement with insulated sandwich panels (80 mm), and individual solar thermal systems for DHW (≈3.9 m² of collectors and 200 l of storage per dwelling).
- Primary framework: Concrete framework + brick walls lacking initial insulation + partial ETICS

The projected GWP for the entire life cycle is roughly 600 kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA, amounting to about 1.17 million kg CO₂-eq for the complete project. This figure positions Brejoeira at the lower spectrum of the impact range noted among the follower cities.

The findings show that, in an Atlantic–Mediterranean climate featuring relatively mild winters, a specific partial renovation (concentrating on the most exposed façades, roof, and essential systems) can attain a positive life-cycle performance. The extra embodied effects of the new insulation and components are counterbalanced by considerable decreases in operational energy needs, even if the intervention falls short of achieving a “deep renovation.”

The Land Use Efficiency measure is near 1.0, indicating the standard density of terraced single-family homes. Although this land-use pattern is not as dense as high-rise buildings, the modest size of the units and the achieved energy enhancements indicate that these

types can still significantly aid local decarbonisation if renovation approaches are effectively focused.

7.1.3.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment for Portugal

The responses submitted by the follower cities have been collected and consolidated. The following table presents the scores provided by each follower city for every indicator, offering a clear overview of their social performance according to the defined reference scale.

Table 18. S-LCIA Results for Portugal

	Indicators	Setubal
<i>Tenants</i>	Accessibility	1
	Health and comfort	0
	Inclusivity	2
	Safety	0
	Affordability	0
<i>Construction Company</i>	Health and safety of workers	0
	Risk assessments	0
<i>Project Owner</i>	Compliance with regulations	2
	Quality assurance	1
	Employee well-being and satisfaction	1
	Stakeholder engagement	1
<i>Local Community</i>	Local employment	0
	Economic development	1
<i>Knowledge and Capacity Development</i>	Energy efficiency awareness	1
	Capacity building activities	0
	Changing attitudes	0
<i>Community Engagement</i>	Level of engagement	1
	Sense of belonging	1

Setúbal performs strongly in Project Owner and Community Engagement, indicating well-structured governance and active stakeholder participation. Lower scores in Construction Company and Knowledge and Capacity Development point to areas where more systematic safety practices or capacity-building actions could be useful.

7.1.3.3 Life Cycle Costing for Portugal

Cost Inventory and General Project Data

This section presents the cost inventory and the main economic and temporal parameters used for the LCC analysis of the Setúbal (Brejoeira) pilot. The objective is to document the input data underpinning the LCC calculation in a transparent and structured manner.

Table 19 summarises the general project information, including the heated floor area (HFA), the applied discount rate, the assumed service life of the main renovation technologies, and the overall reference period. A technology life cycle of 30 years and a 50-year reference period are adopted, in line with the harmonised project methodology.

Table 19. General project information (Setúbal, Brejoeira)

HFA - Heated Floor Area	1,950	m ²
Discount rate	4.5	%
Life cycle of the technologies	30	years
Project lifespan	50	years

The CAPEX inventory for the Setúbal pilot is reported in Table 20 detailing the upfront investment costs associated with the implemented renovation measures and technologies. Figure 2 complements this information by illustrating the breakdown of CAPEX by item within the Construction category, the only category included in the CAPEX inventory, providing a visual representation of each component's relative contribution to total investment costs.

Table 20. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory ((Setúbal-Brejoeira))

Item	Category	Value
Envelope	Construction	274,400.00 €
Windows and Wall Insulations	Construction	104,305.00 €
Solar Panels	Construction	147,600.00 €
TOTAL CAPEX		526,305.00 €

Breakdown Initial CAPEX per Item in the Construction category

Figure 2. Representation of capital expenditure (CAPEX) composition (Setúbal, Breijoiira)

Operational costs are documented in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**, which presents the OPEX inventory, including energy-related costs and other recurring operational, maintenance, and fixed expenses calculated according to the common project assumptions. Figure 3 supports this table by showing the breakdown of OPEX by cost category and highlighting the relative weight of each cost component within the overall operational cost structure.

Table 21. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Setúbal, Breijoiira)

Item	Category	Value	Unit	Price	Unit	Total Cost
Operation and Maintenance costs	Operation & Maintenance	1,5% of CAPEX	%	1.50%	%	7,894.58 €
Replacement and Renewals	Replacement & Renewals	0,7% of CAPEX	%	0.70%	%	3,684.14 €
Fixed expenses (nsurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)	Fixed Expenses	0,8% OF CAPEX	%	0.80%	%	4,210.44 €
Heating	Operating	421,200.00	kWh	0.22	€/kWh	92,664.00 €
Domestic Hot Water	Operating	70,200.00	kWh	0.22	€/kWh	15,444.00 €
Cooling	Operating	37,050.00	kWh	0.22	€/kWh	8,151.00 €

Figure 3. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Setúbal, Breijoiira)

LCC Calculation over the Reference Point

This subsection presents the calculated LCC for the Setúbal (Brejoeira) pilot over the 50-year reference period. Costs are aggregated annually to reflect the temporal distribution of investment, operational, maintenance, and replacement expenditures throughout the building life cycle.

Table 22 reports the year-by-year LCC profile for the Setúbal pilot. Initial investment costs are concentrated in the early years of the analysis period, while OPEX recurs annually during the use phase. Replacement costs for components with service lives shorter than the reference period appear as discrete increases at specific points in time.

The annual LCC representation provides transparency regarding the timing and accumulation of costs over the analysis period, without implying evaluative judgement.

Table 22. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Setúbal, Breijoiira)

Project year	0	1	29	30	31	49	50
Item							Residual Value
Construction Costs	526.305,00 €			251.905,00 €			167.936,67 €
Previous works and demolishing	274.400,00 €			0,00 €			0,00 €

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

<i>Façade works</i>	104.305,00 €			104.305,00 €			69.536,67 €
<i>Insulation, facing, roof and floor insulation</i>	147.600,00 €			147.600,00 €			98.400,00 €
CAPEX	526.305,00 €			251.905,00 €			
Operation and Maintenance costs		7.894,58 €	7.894,58 €	7.894,58 €	7.894,58 €	7.894,58 €	7.894,58 €
Replacement and Renewals		3.684,14 €	3.684,14 €	3.684,14 €	3.684,14 €	3.684,14 €	3.684,14 €
Fixed expenses (insurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)		4.210,44 €	4.210,44 €	4.210,44 €	4.210,44 €	4.210,44 €	4.210,44 €
Heating		92.664,00 €	92.664,00 €	92.664,00 €	92.664,00 €	92.664,00 €	92.664,00 €
Domestic Hot Water		15.444,00 €	15.444,00 €	15.444,00 €	15.444,00 €	15.444,00 €	15.444,00 €
Cooling		8.151,00 €	8.151,00 €	8.151,00 €	8.151,00 €	8.151,00 €	8.151,00 €
OPEX		132.048,15 €	132.048,15 €	132.048,15 €	132.048,15 €	132.048,15 €	132.048,15 €
DISCOUNTED OPEX		126.361,87 €	36.843,42 €	35.256,86 €	33.738,62 €	15.276,86 €	14.619,00 €

LCC Results and Key Indicators

This subsection summarises the LCC results for the Setúbal pilot using aggregated and normalised economic indicators.

Table 23 presents the key LCC indicators, including total nominal LCC, NPC, and EAC. Selected indicators are additionally reported per square metre of heated floor area, enabling scale-independent interpretation of the economic performance.

Table 23. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Setúbal, Breijoiira)

Nominal LCC: nominal life cycle costing	7,212,680.83	€
NPC: net present cost	612,155.85	€
EAC: Equivalent annual cost	37,581.19	€
Nominal LCC per FU: nominal life cycle costing	3,698.81	€/m ²
NPC per FU: net present cost	313.93	€/m ²
EAC per FU: Equivalent annual cost	19.27	€/m ²
OPEX per FU	457.37	€/m ²

To enhance transparency in the aggregation of costs, Table 24 provides a summary of the main discounted cost components contributing to the overall NPC, including discounted CAPEX, discounted OPEX, and residual value.

Table 24. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Setúbal, Brejjoira)

Total CAPEX	778,210.00 €
Total Discounted CAPEX	734,087.08 €
Total OPEX	6,602,407.50 €
Total Discounted OPEX	2,609,536.57 €
Discounted Residual Value	18,592.21 €

Together, these tables provide a consolidated overview of the long-term economic profile associated with the renovation technologies implemented in the Setúbal pilot.

Operational Cost Savings

The expected annual operational savings are reported at the level of the main renovation technologies implemented. The available data allow the attribution of savings to envelope-related measures, wall insulation, and the installation of solar panels.

The combined effect of these measures results in estimated annual savings of approximately 77,900 €, with the largest contribution associated with envelope-related interventions, around 48,700 € per year. Wall insulation measures account for an additional 21,100 € per year, while solar panels contribute approximately 8,100 € per year to the overall savings.

Although the level of detail does not allow a direct linkage between energy carriers and cost reductions, the results indicate that envelope and insulation measures play a dominant role in reducing operational costs in this pilot. The reported values provide an indicative estimate of annual savings under current energy price assumptions.

7.1.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Portugal

The social housing districts in Setúbal, Portugal, present a complex context for energy-efficiency renovation, characterized by high structural vulnerability coexisting with an established, yet uneven, culture of participation.

Economic precarity is the defining feature, leading to pervasive energy poverty: three-quarters of households cannot adequately warm their homes in winter, and two-thirds struggle to cool them in summer. Buildings severely lack insulation and thermal comfort controls. This structural vulnerability explains why the baseline social acceptance of energy-efficiency interventions is intrinsically high, as residents understand the tangible benefits of lower bills and improved health. However, structural accessibility deficits persist inside the buildings, compounding challenges for vulnerable residents.

While the Municipality's participatory initiatives, such as "Nosso Bairro, Nossa Cidade," have fostered a culture of dialogue, producing visible progress in weekly meetings and co-design workshops, participation remains partial. Engagement is largely dominated by active groups

like community leaders, women, and technical staff. Conversely, marginalized groups display significant gaps: the most vulnerable households have very low digital, environmental, and energy literacy (as low as 1/5 on a scale), severely constraining their ability to understand technical proposals. Ethnic minorities and youth participate only minimally. Consequently, decision-making risks being skewed toward better-educated and institutionally connected groups.

High conceptual acceptance does not translate into smooth implementation. The renovation process itself entails significant stressors, including increased noise, temporary loss of access, and potential relocation. These construction disruptions are particularly challenging for elders and people with disabilities. Furthermore, communication channels require strengthening; they often rely too heavily on digital means and fail to translate technical concepts into accessible, experience-based narratives about comfort and savings.

The pathway forward must build on existing strengths, such as active neighbourhood associations and the established participatory governance framework. Trust is increased when communication is continuous and residents can track the visible impact of their contributions. The community possesses key assets in younger generations, students, and environmentally conscious leaders who can act as essential intermediaries. Realizing the full potential requires sustained, inclusive, and empathetic engagement strategies that address both structural inequalities and the daily realities of vulnerability, using embodied, local communication formats to ensure all heterogeneous resident groups co-shape the transition.

7.2 Analysis for Zaragoza, Spain

7.2.1 Technology for Energy Transition

Based on the climatic analysis given in the Section 3.2.1, **Zaragoza** has a strong applicability for cooling-oriented strategies was identified, with cross ventilation, evaporative cooling and mass cooling considered highly relevant, while solar gains and thermal mass remain useful during winter.

Table 25. List of Passive Strategies, Spain

HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS (1)		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation (2)	Evaporative Cooling system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection (3)
Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
X	X		O	O	X	X	X	O

Table 26. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Spain

		HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
		Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation	Evaporative system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection
		Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
Zaragoza	Consumption reduction	-33%	-18%		-37%	-20%	-25%	-36%	-33%	-45%
	Operative temperature	+0.50°C	+0.62°C		0.65°C	0.46°C	-1.21°C	-0.13°C	-0.55°C	-2.03°C

Zaragoza’s weather is characterised by significant differences between the winter and summer seasons, with strong solar exposure. The simulation results show that improving the building envelope and increasing thermal mass provide large heating savings. For cooling, the greatest reduction in energy consumption is linked to installing solar protection in the façade.

This study shows that, in climates with high summer radiation and a wide thermal amplitude, the blueprint should prioritise:

- **Envelope improvement** through increases the insulation façade
- **Optimised external solar protection** together with ventilation strategies and evaporative cooling, to control overheating

7.2.2. Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Spain

- **Spain’s Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan (PRTR – RRF):** Allocates >€12bn to EE in public and private buildings, including new social housing and deep renovation programmes. Component 2 – Housing Renovation and Urban Renewal includes:

- “Programa de rehabilitación para la recuperación económica y social en entornos residenciales” (€3.42bn) for neighbourhood- and building-level renovation.
- Regeneration & Demographic Challenge Programme (€1bn) targeting small municipalities and low-income areas.
- **Cohesion Policy / ERDF support for social housing:** Support for improving the energy efficiency of public social housing in Navarre rehabilitates the public rental housing park with EU funds to tackle energy poverty and cut emissions.
- **Access to ELENA, EEEF, PF4EE, InvestEU:** Spain uses a mix of EU and national grants and repayable instruments (ELENA TA, InvestEU-backed funds, PF4EE credit lines, EEEF) for public and social-building renovation.
- **PREE – Programa de Rehabilitación Energética de Edificios:** National programme for deep EE renovation of existing buildings (envelope, systems, lighting), extended to ~€402.5m and integrated into the PRTR. Offers higher grant rates for condominiums including vulnerable households (social bonus beneficiaries), making it relevant for social housing and low-income blocks.
- **PREE 5000 (Programa de rehabilitación energética para edificios existentes en municipios de reto demográfico):** €50m grant programme targeted at municipalities <5,000 inhabitants, funding insulation, efficient systems, RES, etc. Aims to address climate and demographic challenges; social-housing blocks in small municipalities are eligible alongside private residential buildings.
- **NextGenerationEU housing renovation subsidies (Autonomous Communities):** Autonomous communities manage housing-renovation grant calls financed by PRTR, where any property (including social rental stock) can obtain subsidies if works reduce energy demand/consumption beyond specified thresholds.
- **Specific regional social-housing projects:** Navarre’s RRF and ERDF-co-funded project to rehabilitate its public rental housing stock specifically to increase EE and fight energy poverty. Numerous municipal projects (Soria, Torremolinos) use PRTR housing-renovation lines to upgrade multi-family blocks, often with high shares of low-income/social tenants.
- **National EE lending and green-loan products:** Banks (Santander) offer green loans for building-envelope EE measures, often aligned with PREE / PRTR criteria,

7.2.2.1 Shared Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Zaragoza under the shared savings contract taking into account

increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 14 years, potential energy savings of 53.4% and ROI of 7.78% for social housing and 6.55% to the ESCO.

Table 27. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Spain

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	14	53.38%	7.78%	6.55%	3.99%
Wall	12	27.58%	6.12%	6.45%	3.30%
Roof	13	12.91%	4.03%	5.11%	2.43%
Floor	13	11.94%	3.70%	5.20%	2.18%
Window	19	2.50%	1.77%	2.88%	-0.62%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Zaragoza under the shared savings contract without taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 19 years, potential energy savings of 53.4% and ROI of 3.25% for social housing and 6.55% to the ESCO.

Table 28. Shared Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Spain

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	19	53.38%	3.25%	6.55%	3.99%
Wall	17	27.58%	2.45%	6.45%	3.30%
Roof	18	12.91%	1.45%	5.11%	2.43%
Floor	18	11.94%	1.29%	5.20%	2.18%
Window	23	2.50%	-0.40%	2.88%	-0.62%

7.2.2.2 Guaranteed Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Zaragoza under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented

the expected payback period is 14 years, potential energy savings of 53.4% and ROI of 7.52% for social housing and 5.92% to the ESCO.

Table 29. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value included, Spain

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	19	53.38%	3.25%	6.55%	3.99%
Wall	17	27.58%	2.45%	6.45%	3.30%
Roof	18	12.91%	1.45%	5.11%	2.43%
Floor	18	11.94%	1.29%	5.20%	2.18%
Window	23	2.50%	-0.40%	2.88%	-0.62%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Zaragoza under the guaranteed savings contract without taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 19 years, potential energy savings of 53.4% and ROI of 3.20% for social housing and 5.92% to the ESCO.

Table 30. Guaranteed Savings Contract- Increase in property value not included, Spain

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	19	53.38%	3.20%	5.92%	4.10%
Wall	17	27.58%	2.17%	5.82%	3.40%
Roof	18	12.91%	0.88%	4.61%	2.51%
Floor	18	11.94%	0.67%	4.70%	2.24%
Window	23	2.50%	-0.52%	2.60%	0.64%

7.2.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Spain

7.2.3.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for Spain

Spain is exemplified by two differing instances found in the ACTUR area of Zaragoza:

- ACTUR – Casona: current multifamily structure without energy upgrades, utilized as a reference scenario;
- ACTUR – Emmeline Pankhurst: comparable multifamily building that has experienced a thorough energy upgrade of the facade and windows.

ACTUR – Casona (original state, no upgrades)

- Country: Spain
- Category: Unrenovated multifamily social housing
- GFA: 7,200 m²
- HFA: 6,950.8 m²
- Condition of renovation: Existing building without prior energy renovation; identified as a demo site for future comprehensive renovation in the NEUTRALPATH project.
- Primary system: Reinforced concrete framework + double-section brick walls

The estimated life-cycle GWP is about 870 kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA, totalling roughly 6.05 million kg CO₂-eq. This situation illustrates a standard post-war social housing structure with inadequate insulation, significant thermal losses, and comparatively elevated operational energy requirements.

ACTUR – Emmeline Pankhurst (intense energy refurbishment)

- Country: Spain
- Category: Updated multifamily affordable housing
- GFA: 22,514 m²
- HFA: 19,584 m²
- Condition of renovation: Extensive energy renovation of the building envelope (insulation of facades, roof, and floors in contact with the exterior, and complete replacement of window and door frames). In Building 1, the work has been completed (2022–2023), and in Building 2, the post-renovation state has been modelled, although the work was still in progress at the time of the survey.
- Primary system: Reinforced concrete framework + continuous external cladding (ETICS) + new high-efficiency windows

For Emmeline Pankhurst, the life-cycle GWP per unit area is lowered to around 630 kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA, totalling approximately 12.34 million kg CO₂-eq for the structure. Although ETICS adds more embodied emissions, enhancements in roof and floor insulation along with complete window replacements result in a significant decrease in heating and cooling needs, yielding a net reduction of approximately 27–30% in GWP per m² relative to the non-renovated baseline.

The Land Use Efficiency values are quite elevated in both scenarios (approximately 3.3 for Casona and 3.9 for Emmeline), indicating the compact structure of the ACTUR blocks. In these dense environments, extensive envelope refurbishment proves to be an exceptionally

efficient approach: each m² updated enhances conditions for numerous homes and inhabitants, maximizing the ecological advantage per unit of occupied land.

7.2.3.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment for Spain

Zaragoza demonstrates a balanced performance across most categories, with notable strengths in *Tenants* and *Knowledge and Capacity Development*. A slightly lower score in the *Project Owner* category suggests room to reinforce quality assurance or stakeholder involvement.

Table 31. S-LCIA Results for Spain

Indicators		Zaragoza
<i>Tenants</i>	Accessibility	1
	Health and comfort	1
	Inclusivity	1
	Safety	0
	Affordability	1
<i>Construction Company</i>	Health and safety of workers	0
	Risk assessments	1
<i>Project Owner</i>	Compliance with regulations	1
	Quality assurance	0
	Employee well-being and satisfaction	0
	Stakeholder engagement	0
<i>Local Community</i>	Local employment	0
	Economic development	1
<i>Knowledge and Capacity Development</i>	Energy efficiency awareness	1
	Capacity building activities	0
	Changing attitudes	1
<i>Community Engagement</i>	Level of engagement	0
	Sense of belonging	1

7.2.3.3 Life Cycle Costing For Spain

Cost Inventory and General Project Data

This section presents the cost inventory and the main economic and temporal parameters used for the LCC analysis of the Zaragoza pilot project (ACTUR – Emeline). The objective is to document the input data underpinning the LCC calculation in a transparent and structured manner, without providing interpretation of cost performance.

Table 32 summarises the general project information, including the heated floor area (HFA), the applied discount rate, the assumed service life of the main renovation technologies, and the overall analysis period. A technology life cycle of 30 years and a reference period of 50 years are adopted, in line with the harmonised methodological framework applied across the SUPERSHINE project.

Table 32. General project information (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

HFA - Heated Floor Area	19,584	m ²
Discount rate	4.50	%
Life cycle of the technologies	30	years
Project lifespan	50	years

The Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) inventory for the Zaragoza project is reported in Table 33, detailing the upfront investment costs associated with the implemented renovation measures and technologies. Figure 4 complements this information by illustrating the distribution of CAPEX across the main cost categories, providing a visual representation of the relative contribution of each category to the total investment cost.

Table 33. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Item	Category	Value
Project endorsement	Start-up cost	641.30
Previous works and demolishing	Construction	64,200.23
Façade works	Construction	771,418.72
Insulation, facing, roof and floor insulation	Construction	225,967.60
Exterior windows and doors	Construction	655,380.00
Quality control	Construction	4,747.82
Residues management	Construction	6,333.00
Work health and safety	Construction	172,283.50
13% Operating costs	Operating	247,056.02

6% Industrial profit	Industrial Profit	114,025.86
10% VAT Tax	Tax	226,151.28
TOTAL CAPEX		2,488,205.39 €

Breakdown Initial CAPEX per Category

Figure 4. Breakdown of capital expenditure (CAPEX) by cost category (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Operational costs are documented in Table 34, which presents the Operational Expenditure (OPEX) inventory, including energy-related costs and other recurring operational, maintenance, and fixed expenses calculated according to the common project assumptions. Figure 5 supports this table by showing the breakdown of OPEX components, highlighting their relative weight within the overall operational cost structure.

Table 34. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Item	Category	Value	Unit	Price	Unit	Total Cost
Operation and Maintenance costs	Operation & Maintenance	1.5% of CAPEX	%	1.50%	%	37,323.08
Replacement and Renewals	Replacement & Renewals	0.7% of CAPEX	%	0.70%	%	17,417.44
Fixed expenses (Insurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)	Fixed Expenses	0.8% of CAPEX	%	0.80%	%	19,905.64

Electricity	Operating	57,072.67	kWh	0.1296	€/kWh	7,396,62
Natural gas	Operating	1,769,654.86	kWh	0.0402	€/kWh	71,140.13
Water	Operating	511.00	l/m ²	0.0015	€/l	15,011.14

Figure 5. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

LCC Calculation over the Analysis Period

This section presents the calculated life-cycle costs for the Zaragoza pilot over the 50-year reference period. Costs are aggregated on an annual basis to reflect the temporal distribution of investment, operational, maintenance, and replacement expenses throughout the building life cycle.

Table 35 reports the year-by-year LCC profile for the Zaragoza project. Initial investment costs are concentrated in the early years of the analysis period, while operational and maintenance costs recur annually during the use phase. Replacement costs for components with service lives shorter than the reference period appear as discrete increases at specific points in time.

Table 35. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Project year	0	1	29	30	31	49	50
Item							Residual Value
Start-up Cost	641,30 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
<i>Project endorsement</i>	641,30 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
Construction Costs	1.900.330,93 €			1.900.330,93 €			1.266.887,29 €
<i>Previous works and demolishing</i>	64.200,23 €			64.200,23 €			42.800,15 €
<i>Façade works</i>	771.418,72 €			771.418,72 €			514.279,15 €
<i>Insulation, facing, roof and floor insulation</i>	225.967,60 €			225.967,60 €			150.645,07 €
<i>Exterior windows and doors</i>	655.380,06 €			655.380,06 €			436.920,04 €
<i>Quality control</i>	4.747,82 €			4.747,82 €			3.165,21 €
<i>Residues management</i>	6.333,00 €			6.333,00 €			4.222,00 €
<i>Work health and safety</i>	172.283,50 €			172.283,50 €			114.855,67 €
Operating Costs	247.056,02 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
<i>13% Operating costs</i>	247.056,02 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
Industrial Profit	114.025,86 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
<i>6% Industrial profit</i>	114.025,86 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
Tax	226.151,28 €			226.151,28 €			150.767,52 €
<i>10% VAT Tax</i>	226.151,28 €			226.151,28 €			150.767,52 €
CAPEX	2.488.205,39 €			2.126.482,21 €			
Operation and Maintenance costs		37.323,08 €	37.323,08 €	37.323,08 €	37.323,08 €	37.323,08 €	37.323,08 €
Replacement and Renewals		17.417,44 €	17.417,44 €	17.417,44 €	17.417,44 €	17.417,44 €	17.417,44 €
Fixed expenses (insurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)		19.905,64 €	19.905,64 €	19.905,64 €	19.905,64 €	19.905,64 €	19.905,64 €
Electricity		7.396,62 €	7.396,62 €	7.396,62 €	7.396,62 €	7.396,62 €	7.396,62 €
Natural gas		71.140,13 €	71.140,13 €	71.140,13 €	71.140,13 €	71.140,13 €	71.140,13 €
Water		15.011,14 €	15.011,14 €	15.011,14 €	15.011,14 €	15.011,14 €	15.011,14 €
OPEX		168.194,04 €	168.194,04 €	168.194,04 €	168.194,04 €	168.194,04 €	168.194,04 €
DISCUNTED OPEX		160.951,24 €	46.928,66 €	44.907,81 €	42.973,98 €	19.458,64 €	18.620,70 €

The year-by-year representation allows the evolution of cumulative life-cycle costs to be observed over time and provides transparency regarding the timing of major cost contributions, without implying any evaluative judgement.

LCC Results and Key Indicators

This subsection summarises the LCC results using aggregated and normalised economic indicators.

Table 36 presents the key LCC indicators, including the total nominal Life Cycle Cost over the 50-year analysis period, the Net Present Cost (NPC), and the Equivalent Annual Cost (EAC). Selected indicators are additionally reported per square metre of heated floor area, enabling scale-independent interpretation of the economic performance.

Table 36. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Nominal LCC: nominal life cycle costing	10,339,847.56	€
NPC: net present cost	3,347,000.34	€
EAC: Equivalent annual cost	205,477.52	€
Nominal LCC per FU: nominal life cycle costing	527.97	€/m ²
NPC per FU: net present cost	170.90	€/m ²
EAC per FU: Equivalent annual cost	10.49	€/m ²
OPEX per FU	58.01	€/m ²

To support transparency in the aggregation of life-cycle costs, Table 37 provides a summary of the main discounted cost components contributing to the overall economic results. The table reports the total capital expenditure, operational expenditure, and residual value expressed in discounted terms, allowing the relative contribution of each component to the Net Present Cost to be clearly identified.

Table 37. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Zaragoza – ACTUR Emeline)

Total CAPEX	4,614,687.60 €
Total Discounted CAPEX	3,055,976.17 €
Total OPEX	8,409,702.06 €
Total Discounted OPEX	3,323,851.95 €
Discounted Residual Value	291,024.17 €

Together, these tables provide a consolidated overview of the long-term economic profile associated with the implemented renovation technologies, linking detailed cost inventories and annual cost development to aggregated life-cycle cost indicators.

Operational Cost Savings

Annual operational savings are estimated based on the reduction in final energy consumption following the renovation. The assessment considers changes in electricity and natural gas consumption between the pre- and post-renovation conditions.

The results indicate a reduction in annual electricity-related costs of approximately 3,700 € per dwelling, alongside a substantially larger reduction in natural gas expenditure, amounting to approximately 49,700 € per year. Taken together, the total expected annual savings associated with reduced energy consumption are estimated at around 53,500 €.

These figures illustrate the significant contribution of reduced energy demand, particularly for heating, to operational cost savings in this pilot. Given the limited resolution of the available data, the values should be interpreted as indicative of the scale of savings rather than as precise forecasts.

7.2.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Spain

The Actur Rey Fernando district in Zaragoza presents a contrasting picture of advanced infrastructure and strategic planning alongside significant social and participatory asymmetries in the context of energy renovation.

The city benefits from solid municipal infrastructure, strong environmental planning, and robust social integration frameworks like the Cultural and Solidarity House, which offers specialized support for foreign residents and ethnic minorities. Zaragoza Vivienda further supports social housing families through the CEDIS Social Dynamisation and Labour Centre, providing critical social support, training, and a hub for participation that bypasses inaccessible digital channels.

Despite this institutional commitment, the capacity of residents to engage meaningfully is highly variable. The district has a predominance of older residents, with almost half of the population aged over fifty, many of whom face digital and energy literacy challenges. Vulnerable households, the elderly, and people with disabilities repeatedly show very low capacity to engage with technical content.

The urgency for change is fueled by economic fragility, evidenced by a notable vacancy rate, rent default rates, and high energy costs, averaging around €2,536 a year per household. A significant share of residents still struggles to maintain adequate indoor warmth.

Actur is an important site for infrastructural innovation, hosting a pioneering district-heating network, biomass pilots, and collective self-consumption models like "Barrio Solar." This ecosystem should support high social acceptance. However, residents' energy literacy remains very low, limiting their capacity to fully appreciate the benefits without targeted mediation.

A structural gap exists in participation: engagement is strong in social, cultural, and integration contexts, but weak in technical and infrastructural planning. Local neighborhood associations have not been directly involved in energy-efficiency refurbishment decisions. Social acceptance of renovation, while likely high in principle due to promised benefits, may falter during implementation unless key barriers are addressed:

- Low Literacy and Awareness: Residents lack awareness of passive and active energy-saving measures.
- Absence from Decision-Making: Vulnerable groups are not actively shaping refurbishment plans.
- Communication: Processes must be tailored, face-to-face, and empathetic, rather than relying on abstract consultation or digital means.

The district's potential lies in mobilizing existing assets: students and municipal professionals with high digital literacy can act as mediators, and the City's commitment to sustainability provides a coherent strategic narrative. The future success of renovation hinges on bridging the gap between technical innovation and inclusive social processes, ensuring that assets are mobilized to overcome structural limitations, turning Actur into a model where innovation and social inclusion mutually reinforce each other.

7.3 Analysis for Belgrade, Serbia

7.3.1 Technology for Energy Transition

Based on the climatic analysis given in the Section 3.2.1, Belgrade shows similar requirements, with high relevance for both heating and cooling approaches, where thermal mass, solar gains, natural ventilation, evaporative cooling and shading devices help maintain indoor comfort.

Table 38. List of Passive Strategies, Serbia

HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS (1)		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation (2)	Evaporative Cooling system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection (3)
Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
X	X		○	○	X	X	X	○

Table 39. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Serbia

HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation	Evaporative system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection

		Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
Belgrade	Consumption reduction	-19%	-12%		-29%	-17%	-11%	-40%	-35%	-42%
	Operative temperature	+0.50°C	+0.54°C		0.86°C	0.8°C	-0.74°C	-0.3°C	-0.58°C	-2.13°C

Belgrade has a humid temperate climate with a strong continental influence, with cold winters and hot summers and a clear seasonal temperature gap. The heating results show sensitivity to improvements in the building envelope and to replacing windows and doors. Because of this contrast between winter and summer, thermal mass becomes an effective support once the envelope is improved. In summer, the greatest reductions in cooling demand come from external solar protection, with thermal mass helping to keep indoor temperatures more stable and reduce overheating.

In Belgrade’s climate, the blueprint should prioritise envelope retrofitting and window/door replacement for winter resilience, and make external solar shading a mandatory summer action, complemented by thermal mass actions.

7.3.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition in Serbia

- **Regional Energy Efficiency Programme (REEP, REEP Plus – WBIF, EBRD, EU):** Multi-country Western Balkans programme providing policy support, TA and financing for EE in buildings, including in Serbia; supports municipal and residential projects via blended finance.
- **EBRD Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF) – Serbia:** EU- and donor-supported facility where households and housing associations can obtain loans from local partner banks to invest in EE measures (insulation, windows, boilers, etc.) in apartment buildings.
- **Serbia Residential Clean Energy and Energy Efficiency Scale-Up Project (P176770):** Structured around (i) partial grants and financing for EE, sustainable heating and rooftop solar in residential buildings – with a focus on lower-income households, and (ii) capacity-building and development of scalable financing mechanisms (e.g., revolving funds, on-bill repayment).
- **WBIF & KfW “Energy Efficiency Programme in Public Buildings / Central Government Buildings”:** EBRD/KfW loans plus EU grants for EE renovation of schools and central government buildings (e.g., Belgrade CGB programme), building

capacity and local supply chains that can also support future social-housing renovations.

- Public ESCO Project – Subsidies for Energy Renovation of Residential Buildings:** Launched by the Ministry of Mining and Energy with EBRD support, the Public ESCO project provides subsidies to housing associations: grants cover energy-efficiency studies and 50% of renovation works, with the remaining 50% repaid by residents over ~10 years (estimated ~€2,500 per 50m² flat). Focuses on multi-apartment buildings (many with low-income households) connected to district heating, aiming to cut consumption and introduce consumption-based billing.
- Residential Clean Energy & EE Scale-Up (national implementation):** The World Bank-backed project is being implemented by Serbian authorities as a national mechanism combining grants and concessional loans for EE and small-scale renewables in homes, including multi-apartment and (de facto) social housing; it is designed to become a scalable national EE financing framework.

7.3.2.1 Shared Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Serbia under the shared savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 58.53% and ROI of 10.64% for social housing and 9.13% to the ESCO.

Table 40. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Serbia

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	58.53%	10.64%	9.13%	4.84%
Wall	11	33.13%	8.37%	8.98%	4.01%
Roof	12	18.70%	5.52%	7.22%	2.96%
Floor	12	17.74%	5.05%	7.15%	2.65%
Window	18	8.45%	2.42%	4.01%	0.75%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Serbia under the shared savings contract without taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented

the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 58.53% and ROI of 5.85% for social housing and 9.13% to the ESCO.

Table 41. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Serbia

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	58.53%	5.85%	9.13%	4.84%
Wall	15	33.13%	4.60%	8.98%	4.01%
Roof	16	18.70%	3.03%	7.22%	2.96%
Floor	16	17.74%	2.78%	7.15%	2.65%
Window	22	8.45%	1.33%	4.01%	0.75%

7.3.2.2 Guaranteed savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Serbia under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 58.53% and ROI of 11.44% for social housing and 9.62% to the ESCO.

Table 42. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Serbia

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	58.53%	11.44%	9.62%	5.21%
Wall	11	33.13%	8.99%	9.47%	4.31%
Roof	12	18.70%	5.93%	7.61%	3.18%
Floor	12	17.74%	5.43%	7.54%	2.85%
Window	18	8.45%	2.60%	4.23%	0.81%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Serbia under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 58.53% and ROI of 6.28% for social housing and 9.62% to the ESCO.

Table 43. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Serbia

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	58.33%	6.28%	9.62%	5.21%
Wall	15	33.13%	4.94%	9.47%	4.31%
Roof	16	18.70%	3.26%	7.61%	3.18%
Floor	16	17.74%	2.98%	7.54%	2.85%
Window	22	8.45%	1.43%	4.23%	0.81%

7.3.3 LCA and S-LCIA for Serbia

7.3.3.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for Serbia

The Serbian case study is a large-scale multifamily building in New Belgrade, constructed with a prefabricated IMS concrete system and subject to a deep energy renovation scenario including ETICS and high-performance glazing.

- Country: Serbia
- Category: Large-scale multifamily housing
- GFA: 12,800 m²
- HFA: 9,100 m²
- Condition of renovation: A deep energy renovation scenario has been defined based on:
 - adding an ETICS-type facade (contact facade) with 10–20 cm of additional insulation to “External wall 1”;
 - complete renovation of the roof with 16–25 cm of new insulation;
 - possible widespread replacement of windows with triple-glazed PVC frames (1.0–1.2 W/m²K), currently considered an optional measure;
 - incorporation of cost allocators, heat meters at the dwelling level, and thermostatic valves on radiators.
- Primary system: IMS prefabricated concrete structure + ETICS + triple glazing

The estimated life-cycle GWP is about 990 kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA, resulting in a total of approximately 9.01 million kg CO₂-eq. This is the highest specific GWP among the analysed follower projects

Two main factors explain this result:

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

- The structural system is highly material-intensive (prefabricated heavy concrete), leading to a significant embodied impact; and
- The building is located in a continental climate with cold winters and hot summers, where operational energy demand is substantial and still largely supplied by fossil-based district heating.

Even with a deep renovation, the combined effect of a heavy structural system and a carbon-intensive energy mix maintains the GWP at a high level. This underlines an important message for the Blueprint: in contexts like Belgrade, building-level efficiency measures must be complemented by decarbonisation of the district-heating system and broader energy-system reforms to fully unlock environmental benefits.

The Land Use Efficiency is high (around 6.0), indicating an intensive use of land and a strong potential impact per unit of plot area. When deep renovation is applied to such large, dense blocks, the cumulative benefit at neighbourhood scale can be very significant, provided that the upstream energy mix is also addressed.

7.3.3.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Belgrade performs particularly well in *Local Community*, reflecting strong expected benefits in employment and economic development, and also scores highly in *Community Engagement* and *Knowledge and Capacity Development*. However, neutral scores in *Construction Company* and *Project Owner* suggest opportunities to strengthen operational processes and internal quality mechanisms.

Table 44. S-LCIA Results for Serbia

Indicators		Belgrade
<i>Tenants</i>	Accessibility	-1
	Health and comfort	1
	Inclusivity	0
	Safety	0
	Affordability	1
<i>Construction Company</i>	Health and safety of workers	0
	Risk assessments	0
<i>Project Owner</i>	Compliance with regulations	0
	Quality assurance	-1
	Employee well-being and satisfaction	0
	Stakeholder engagement	2
<i>Local Community</i>	Local employment	2

	Economic development	2
<i>Knowledge and Capacity Development</i>	Energy efficiency awareness	1
	Capacity building activities	1
	Changing attitudes	1
<i>Community Engagement</i>	Level of engagement	1
	Sense of belonging	1

7.3.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in the Serbia

Block 29 in New Belgrade is defined by a tension between its robust historical urban planning and contemporary governance deficits that hinder energy efficiency renovation. The district possesses strong assets: high-quality local infrastructure (schools, green spaces, transport), a functional district heating system, and a highly educated population with high employment and technical competence (including engineers and academics).

However, these strengths are counterbalanced by deep structural barriers:

- **Top-Down Governance and Disengagement:** The system is highly centralized. Decisions on renovation, subsidies, and investment are made at the Ministry or City level, with virtually no district-level citizen involvement. The lack of smart grids or community-driven energy solutions reflects this technological and organizational gap. Despite the high digital and technical literacy of residents, the absence of institutionalized participatory channels leaves them structurally disengaged. Social-housing residents are particularly vulnerable, lacking representation.
- **Erosion of Trust and Unequal Allocation:** The broader Serbian context of political tensions and a perceived lack of transparency has created widespread scepticism. This mistrust is reinforced by national energy schemes, such as the public ESCO program, which has been criticized for favoring high-value neighborhoods (apartments exceeding €2,500/m²) while neglecting poorer districts. This unequal allocation, combined with a lack of clarity in financial flows, severely damages the public credibility of renovation efforts.
- **Minimal Participation and Inertia:** Community participation is minimal, limited to information sessions rather than co-creation. The legal and ownership structures of post-socialist housing have not been adapted to facilitate shared decision-making, resulting in institutional inertia. This lack of co-design, reflected in national debates on condominium conflicts, increases residents' anxiety about rising costs and construction disruption.
- **External Pressures:** Local concerns over real-estate development and proposals for new high-rise buildings on green plots create intense mistrust. Residents perceive

municipal decisions as prioritizing private commercial interests, complicating the acceptance of any urban intervention, including energy renovation, which risks being perceived as another top-down imposition.

In summary, Block 29 has the necessary technical and human capital for a successful energy transition, but social acceptance is heavily mediated by trust, transparency, and procedural fairness. Future success depends on creating accessible, intuitive, and locally meaningful engagement tools that leverage the existing engineering knowledge while explicitly addressing the anxieties of vulnerable groups regarding cost calculation and subsidy fairness. Without restoring a sense of co-creation, acceptance will remain conditional, vulnerable to the social and political uncertainty shaping Serbian urban life.

7.4 Analysis for Kadıköy, Türkiye

7.4.1 Technology for Energy Transition

Based on the climatic analysis given in the Section 3.2.1, Kadikoy presents a balanced need across seasons, with thermal mass, solar gains and thermal insulation supporting winter comfort, and cross ventilation, mass cooling and solar protection supporting summer conditions.

Table 45. List of Passive Strategies, Türkiye

HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS (1)		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation (2)	Evaporative Cooling system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection (3)
Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
X	X	X	○	○	X		X	○

Table 46. Reduction in Energy Consumption and Operative Temperature, Türkiye

		HEATING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			RETROFITTING ACTIONS		COOLING PASSIVE STRATEGIES			
		Thermal Mass	Solar Gains	Thermal Insulation	Replace joinery	Thermal Envelope	Cross Ventilation	Evaporative system	Thermal Mass	Solar Protection
		Active Solar Heating	Passive Solar Heating	Internal Gains	Improve envelope	Thermal envelope	Natural Ventilation	Evaporative Cooling	Mass Cooling	Shading Devices
Kadikoy	Consumption	-22%	-11%	-17%	-38%	-22%	-8%		-37%	-39%

reduction										
Operative temperature	+0.57°C	+0.43°C	+0.96°C	0.89°C	0.76°C	-0.81°C			-0.61°C	-1.82°C

Kadıköy has the same Köppen–Geiger climate as Setúbal. In this context, the climate is drier and colder in winter than in the previous case. The heating results show that, once the envelope is improved, thermal mass works successfully because this climate has thermal changes, giving more opportunity to benefit from inertia and improve user comfort.

In summer, solar shading is one of the most effective measures to reduce cooling demand. In this case, thermal mass also helps.

For this climate, the main priorities are:

- Improve the envelope to cut winter heat losses.
- Use optimised solar shading together with thermal mass cooling to limit summer overheating.

In this context, thermal mass should be considered a key design criterion, as it reduces heating demand and also lowers cooling needs.

7.4.2 Funding Mechanisms and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building Stock Energy Transition Investments in Türkiye

- **TuREEFF - Turkish Residential Energy Efficiency Financing Facility (EBRD)**⁷: A dedicated credit line for residential EE, channelled via local banks, originally around €300 million.
- **TurSEFF – Turkey Sustainable Energy Financing Facility (EBRD)**⁸: A €400m facility providing credit lines to Turkish banks and leasing companies for sustainable energy investments by SMEs and public entities, including building EE (municipal housing and public buildings).
- **IPA-funded “Energy Efficiency in Buildings (IEEB)” project**⁹: EU IPA project to align Turkey’s building-EE legislation with the EU acquis and promote EE in buildings, with partners including the Housing Development Administration (TOKİ).
- **TOKİ social-housing programme**¹⁰: TOKİ (Housing Development Administration) has built 1.7 million social housing units and is launching new large-scale programmes (2025 initiative for hundreds of thousands of homes), with increasing emphasis on seismic safety and modern building standards, including EE

⁷ https://ebrdgeff.com/seff_facilities/turkiye-residential/

⁸ <https://www.ebrd.com/home/work-with-us/projects/psd/52713.html>

⁹ https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/a42b6fa6-d326-42ae-aa2d-17d53329190e_en?filename=tr2011.0465.20_energy_efficiency_in_buildings.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.toki.gov.tr/en/housing-programs.html>

requirements. While not an explicit “EE retrofit fund,” TOKİ’s investments are a major channel to deliver new, more energy-efficient social housing and can incorporate EE renovation in urban renewal areas.

- **National EE loans and incentives for households¹¹:** Households can use TuREEFF loans for EE upgrades in apartment blocks, including those that are effectively social or low-income housing, as long as they meet the bank’s criteria.

7.4.2.1 Shared Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Turkey under the shared savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 61.22% and ROI of 8.60% for social housing and 7.24% to the ESCO.

Table 47. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Türkiye

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	61.22%	8.60%	7.24%	4.40%
Wall	11	34.66%	6.76%	7.12%	3.65%
Roof	12	19.56%	4.45%	5.64%	2.69%
Floor	12	18.56%	4.08%	5.75%	2.41%
Window	18	8.84%	1.96%	3.18%	0.68%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Turkey under the shared savings contract without taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 61.22% and ROI of 5.42% for social housing and 7.24% to the ESCO.

Table 48. Shared Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Türkiye

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	61.22%	5.42%	7.24%	4.40%
Wall	15	34.66%	4.26%	7.12%	3.65%

¹¹<https://resourcehub.bakermckenzie.com/en/resources/global-sustainable-buildings/europe-middle-east-and-africa/turkiye/topics/financing>

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

Roof	16	19.56%	2.81%	5.64%	2.69%
Floor	16	18.56%	2.57%	5.75%	2.41%
Window	22	8.84%	1.23%	3.18%	0.68%

7.4.2.2 Guaranteed Savings contract

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Turkey under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 13 years, potential energy savings of 61.22% and ROI of 9.77% for social housing and 8.22% to the ESCO.

Table 49. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value included, Türkiye

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	13	61.22%	9.77%	8.22%	5.01%
Wall	11	34.66%	7.68%	8.09%	4.15%
Roof	12	19.56%	5.06%	6.42%	3.06%
Floor	12	18.56%	4.64%	6.53%	2.74%
Window	18	8.84%	2.22%	3.61%	0.77%

The table below provides the payback period, expected energy savings and the Return on Investment (ROI) for the implementation of all SUPERSHINE proposed EE renovations as a bundle and separately in Turkey under the guaranteed savings contract taking into account increase in property market value. In the case all EE renovations are implemented the expected payback period is 17 years, potential energy savings of 61.22% and ROI of 6.16% for social housing and 8.22% to the ESCO.

Table 50. Guaranteed Savings Contract - Increase in property value not included, Türkiye

	Payback period	Energy savings	ROI		
			Social housing	ESCO	Tenants
All interventions	17	61.22%	6.16%	8.22%	5.01%
Wall	15	34.66%	4.84%	8.09%	4.15%
Roof	16	19.56%	3.19%	6.42%	3.06%
Floor	16	18.56%	2.93%	6.53%	2.74%
Window	22	8.84%	1.40%	3.61%	0.77%

7.4.3 LCA, S-LCIA and LCC for Türkiye

7.4.3.1 Life Cycle Assessment for Türkiye

For Türkiye, the representative case is Kadıköy, a large multifamily ensemble of 17 blocks in Istanbul, currently in a state of partial renovation. The structural system is based on reinforced concrete with ceramic infill walls, and some limited improvements (such as window replacement and interior lighting upgrades) have already been implemented.

- Country: Türkiye
- Category: Multifamily housing (17 blocks)
- GFA: 62,837.5 m²
- HFA: 51,500 m²
- Condition of renovation: Existing park without comprehensive renovation, in which specific actions have already been carried out, mainly the replacement of some of the windows and the partial renovation of the interior lighting to LED technology. In addition, the files include proposals for improving the opaque envelope and other systems, which are still in the planning stage.
- Primary system: Reinforced concrete structure + ceramic infill walls

The life-cycle GWP is estimated at around 850 kg CO₂-eq/m² HFA, with a total impact of approximately 43.78 million kg CO₂-eq for the whole ensemble. This places Kadıköy in an intermediate position between the lower values observed in Portugal and Spain's deep-renovation case, and the higher values in Belgrade.

From an LCA perspective, Kadıköy illustrates a common situation in large social-housing estates:

- Partial, uncoordinated interventions (e.g. replacement of some windows, local lighting upgrades) yield limited life-cycle benefits when the thermal envelope remains largely unimproved;
- The scale of the ensemble means that even moderate improvements can translate into large absolute reductions of emissions, but this potential is only realised if a coherent, district-level renovation strategy is implemented.

The current data do not allow a robust Land Use Efficiency value to be calculated (the indicator is not available for this case). However, the typology is clearly dense and multi-storey, suggesting that Kadıköy could deliver very high environmental and social returns if deep renovation packages (external insulation, systematic window replacement, efficient systems and renewables) are deployed in a coordinated way across the 17 blocks.

7.4.3.2 Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Kadıköy shows positive results in *Project Owner* and *Community Engagement*, but the negative score under *Construction Company* suggests challenges related to health and safety or risk assessment procedures. Lower values in *Local Community* and *Tenants* indicate the need for improved actions toward community benefits and tenant-related aspects.

Table 51. S-LCIA Results for Türkiye

Subcategories	Indicators	Kadikoy
<i>Tenants</i>	Accessibility	0
	Health and comfort	0
	Inclusivity	0
	Safety	-1
	Affordability	-1
<i>Construction Company</i>	Health and safety of workers	-1
	Risk assessments	-1
<i>Project Owner</i>	Compliance with regulations	1
	Quality assurance	1
	Employee well-being and satisfaction	1
	Stakeholder engagement	0
<i>Local Community</i>	Local employment	-1
	Economic development	0
<i>Knowledge and Capacity Development</i>	Energy efficiency awareness	0
	Capacity building activities	-1
	Changing attitudes	1
<i>Community Engagement</i>	Level of engagement	1
	Sense of belonging	0

7.4.3.3 Life Cycle Costing For Türkiye

Cost Inventory and General Project Data

This section presents the cost inventory and the main economic and temporal parameters used for the Life Cycle Costing analysis of the Istanbul (Kadiköy) pilot. The objective is to document the input data underpinning the LCC calculation in a transparent and structured manner, without providing interpretation of cost performance.

Table 52 summarises the general project information, including the heated floor area (HFA), the applied discount rate, the assumed service life of the main renovation technologies, and the overall analysis period. In line with the harmonised methodological framework adopted within the SUPERSHINE project, a technology life cycle of 30 years and a reference period of 50 years are applied.

Table 52. General project information (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

HFA - Heated Floor Area	11,638	m ²
Discount rate	4.5	%
Life cycle of the technologies	30	years
Project lifespan	50	years

The Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) inventory for the Istanbul (Kadiköy) pilot is reported in Table 53. The table presents the total upfront investment cost associated with the implemented renovation measures and technologies. Where a detailed breakdown of investment items was not available, the allocation of costs across cost elements is based on reasoned assumptions consistent with the scope of the renovation and the adopted methodological framework. This approach allows the composition of the initial investment to be represented in a transparent and structured manner. Figure 6 supports this table by showing the breakdown of OPEX components.

Table 53. Capital expenditure (CAPEX) inventory (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

Item	Percentage	Value
Demolition/Dismantling	10.00%	722,690.30 €
Technology Implementation	70.00%	5,058,832.10 €
Other costs (design, scaffolding, operating, overheads, permits)	20.00%	1,445,380.60 €
TOTAL CAPEX		7,226,903.00 €

Figure 6. Representation of capital expenditure (CAPEX) composition (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

Operational costs are documented in Table 54, which presents the OPEX inventory. The table includes energy-related costs as well as recurring operation, maintenance, replacement, and fixed expenses, calculated according to the common assumptions applied across all pilot cases. Together, the CAPEX and OPEX inventories define the cost inputs used for the subsequent life-cycle cost calculation.

Table 54. Operational expenditure (OPEX) inventory (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

Item	Category	Value	Unit	Price	Unit	Total Cost
Operation and Maintenance costs	Operation & Maintenance		%		%	43,289.00 €
Replacement and Renewals	Replacement & Renewals	0.7% of CAPEX	%	0.70%	%	50,588.32 €
Fixed expenses (Insurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)	Fixed Expenses	0.8% of CAPEX	%	0.80%	%	57,815.22 €
Heating Demand	Operating	1,753,730.22	kWh	0.02	€/kWh	35,074.60 €
Hot Water Demand	Operating	1,404,590.22	kWh	0.02	€/kWh	28,091.80 €
Cooling Demand	Operating	1,753,730.22	kWh	0.02	€/kWh	35,074.60 €

Electricity Demand	Operating	2,104,499.54	kWh	0.05	€/kWh	105,224.98 €
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Figure 7. Breakdown of operational expenditure (OPEX) by cost category (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

LCC Calculation over the Reference Period

This subsection presents the calculated life-cycle costs for the Istanbul (Kadiköy) pilot over the 50-year reference period. Costs are aggregated on an annual basis to reflect the temporal distribution of investment, operational, maintenance, and replacement expenditures throughout the building life cycle.

Table 55 reports the year-by-year LCC profile for the Istanbul (Kadiköy) pilot. Initial investment costs are concentrated in the early years of the analysis period, while operational and maintenance costs recur annually during the use phase. Replacement costs for components with service lives shorter than the reference period appear as discrete cost increases at specific points in time. Residual values are accounted for at the end of the analysis period, reflecting the remaining service life of relevant components.

Table 55. Year-by-year life cycle cost over the 50-year reference period (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

Project year	0	1	29	30	31	49	50
Item							Residual Value

D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

Demolition and Technology Implementation costs	7.226.903,00 €			6.504.212,70 €			4.336.141,80 €
<i>Demolition/Dismantling</i>	722.690,30 €			0,00 €			0,00 €
<i>Technology Implementation</i>	5.058.832,10 €			5.058.832,10 €			3.372.554,73 €
<i>Other costs (design, scaffolding, operating, overheads, permits)</i>	1.445.380,60 €			1.445.380,60 €			963.587,07 €
CAPEX	7.226.903,00 €			6.504.212,70 €			
Operation and Maintenance costs		43.289,00 €	43.289,00 €	43.289,00 €	43.289,00 €	43.289,00 €	43.289,00 €
Replacement and Renewals		50.588,32 €	50.588,32 €	50.588,32 €	50.588,32 €	50.588,32 €	50.588,32 €
Fixed expenses (insurance, property tax (IBI), administration, basic facility management.)		57.815,22 €	57.815,22 €	57.815,22 €	57.815,22 €	57.815,22 €	57.815,22 €
Electricity		35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €
Natural gas		28.091,80 €	28.091,80 €	28.091,80 €	28.091,80 €	28.091,80 €	28.091,80 €
Water		35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €	35.074,60 €
OPEX		249.933,56 €	249.933,56 €	249.933,56 €	249.933,56 €	249.933,56 €	249.933,56 €
DISCUNTED OPEX		239.170,87 €	69.735,22 €	66.732,26 €	63.858,63 €	28.915,21 €	27.670,06 €

LCC Results and Key Indicators

This subsection summarises the Life Cycle Costing results for the Istanbul (Kadiköy) pilot using aggregated and normalised economic indicators.

Table 56 presents the key LCC indicators, including the total nominal Life Cycle Cost over the 50-year analysis period, the Net Present Cost (NPC), and the Equivalent Annual Cost (EAC). Selected indicators are additionally reported per square metre of heated floor area, enabling scale-independent interpretation and consistency with the presentation of results for the other pilot cases.

Table 56. Life cycle cost results and key indicators (Istanbul – Kadiköy)

Nominal LCC: nominal life cycle costing	21,891,651.81	€
NPC: net present cost	9,443,580.63	€
EAC: Equivalent annual cost	579,755.99	€
Nominal LCC per FU: nominal life cycle costing	1,881.05	€/m ²
NPC per FU: net present cost	811.44	€/m ²
EAC per FU: Equivalent annual cost	49.82	€/m ²
OPEX per FU	145.05	€/m ²

To further support transparency in the aggregation of life-cycle costs, Table 57 provides a summary of the main discounted cost components contributing to the Net Present Cost. The table reports discounted capital expenditure, discounted operational expenditure, and residual values, allowing the relative contribution of investment and use-phase costs to the overall economic profile to be clearly identified.

Table 57. Summary of discounted life cycle cost components (Istanbul – Kadıköy)

Total CAPEX	13,731,115.70 €
Total Discounted CAPEX	10,893,11.10 €
Total OPEX	12,496,677.91 €
Total Discounted OPEX	4,939,188.92 €
Discounted Residual Value	480,052.74 €

Together, these tables provide a consolidated overview of the long-term economic profile associated with the renovation technologies implemented in the Istanbul (Kadıköy) pilot.

Operational Cost Savings

For the Istanbul (Kadıköy) pilot, information on operational cost savings is limited to an aggregate estimate of annual savings resulting from reduced energy consumption following renovation.

Based on the available data, the expected annual operational savings are estimated at approximately 5,760 €. Due to data constraints, this value is not disaggregated by energy carrier or technology and should be interpreted as an indicative aggregate figure.

Despite the limited level of detail, the reported savings highlight the contribution of improved operational performance to the overall life-cycle cost profile of the pilot.

7.4.4 State of Play Regarding Engagement and Social Acceptance in Türkiye

Kadıköy, Istanbul, is a highly urbanized and structurally vulnerable district where the feasibility and social acceptance of energy-efficiency interventions are profoundly shaped by its unique dynamics. The district's primary concern is seismic safety, which stands as an unequivocal priority above energy efficiency in both public perception and municipal policy. The building stock is predominantly old and structurally fragile, making earthquake preparedness a psychological imperative. Consequently, residents view seismic strengthening as the necessary precondition for any further investment, relegating thermal comfort and reduced energy bills to secondary or distant concerns.

Urban renewal is heavily driven by the market-centered 2012 Urban Transformation Law, which accelerates demolition and reconstruction. This framework focuses on maximizing

property value (financial gains, extra floor space) rather than enhancing environmental performance. The absence of a social housing tradition and the market-driven approach mean concepts like community-led retrofitting or shared energy systems are foreign to the local governance culture. Reconstruction also frequently causes gentrification and the displacement of tenants, which has weakened the social networks necessary for coordinated energy-efficiency initiatives.

The district's built environment exhibits poor thermal, but unlike European pilot districts, Kadıköy lacks district heating, shared energy systems, or co-generation infrastructure. Renewable energy penetration is minimal, although the municipality has made a pioneering move by mandating solar systems for buildings above a certain floor area. Technologically, digitalisation is modest. Digital literacy varies sharply, creating a digital divide: professionals have above-average skills, while vulnerable groups and the elderly exhibit limited familiarity. This gap limits the reach of digital engagement tools.

In terms of social dynamics, community-based structures dedicated to housing issues are largely absent. Cooperatives function as mere administrative bodies, and there is no established culture of tenant involvement in refurbishment. Low-income support exists through general social assistance, not targeted energy renovation schemes. Economic instability has made residents risk-averse, meaning they refrain from investing in non-structural upgrades without strong guarantees. Consequently, trust is a central obstacle, extending to institutions, technical solutions, and financial models related to energy-efficiency projects.

Despite these barriers, Kadıköy possesses significant strengths. It is one of Türkiye's most forward-looking municipalities in climate governance, being a signatory of the Covenant of Mayors and having developed a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan. The municipality has proven institutional capacity to mobilize stakeholders and launch awareness campaigns.

In conclusion, Kadıköy's path toward accepting large-scale energy efficiency is obstructed not by opposition, but by a layered system of priorities dictated by seismic risk and a market-driven urban renewal model. Success requires an integrated engagement strategy that leverages the municipality's progressive policies and introduces energy efficiency not as an optional addition, but as a fundamental component of safe, modern, and economically viable urban transformation.

8. Replication Guidelines

This section brings together the key conditions required to replicate the SUPERSHINE approach in different cities with varying urban contexts. The Guidelines are structured as a sequential pathway, starting from the social conditions for engagement, moving through the environmental and economic performance of renovation options and concluding with the policy and organisational enablers required to scale up implementation. Despite attempts at harmonization at EU scale, significant variations still exist in policy and legislative strategies and practices by national governments, no doubt mediated by historical underpinnings, which no doubt is doubly true for the non-EU cities.

8.1 Social Acceptance through Engagement

Deep renovation of social housing cannot rely on technical and/or financial solutions alone: indeed, across Europe, energy-efficiency interventions often fail not because of weak engineering, but because they collide with everyday realities, such as primarily, “the investment deficit”, limited household budgets, uneven literacy, fragile trust in institutions, and competing priorities such as seismic safety or housing affordability. The SUPERSHINE model of “acceptance through engagement” responds to this challenge by placing people, with their vulnerabilities, expectations, memories and aspirations, at the centre of the renovation journey.

At its core lies a simple but transformative assumption, that is to say that social acceptance is not a precondition of renovation, but a product of it. This is something that must be built deliberately, through transparent communication, shared decision-making, and continuous, face-to-face presence in the community. The model rejects one-off consultations in favour of a long arc of engagement that evolves from early listening to co-design, and from disruption management to post-renovation empowerment.

The blueprint that follows translates this ethos into a phased process that cities can adopt and adapt, and each phase is enriched with concrete practices from the SUPERSHINE lighthouses of Riga, in Latvia, Trieste, in Italy, and Herring, in Denmark, as well as criticalities and existing good practices from the current landscape condition of the fellow cities.

Phased approach

The phases presented below do not simply follow a chronological renovation workflow: they are the outcome of a deliberate process of translation from SUPERSHINE’s strategic framework (D1.2), its on-the-ground engagement and co-creation experiences (D1.4), and the cross-country comparative analysis. It needs to be emphasized that the previous framing

regarding the unique policy, technical and economical evaluations set the boundaries of the potential interventions. The adaptation follows three steps.

First, the project examined what, across the four districts, (and building on the country specific foundational analyses in the policy, technical, financial and environmental domains detailed in previous sections of the Report), made engagement succeed or not: patterns emerged, i.e. social acceptance improved when residents saw visible responses to their concerns, while it declined when communication arrived too late or felt abstract. Furthermore, it strengthened when trust was nurtured through continuity and transparency, while it weakened when renovation disrupted everyday life without adequate support. These insights guided the identification of the critical “pressure points” in the renovation journey.

Second, these pressure points were reorganised into a logical sequence that mirrors the lived experience of residents, giving more weight to early listening, sustained presence during disruptions, and post-renovation empowerment, elements often underplayed in conventional technical planning.

Third, each phase was enriched with contextual insights from the four fellow cities. Therefore, the model has become modular and locally adaptable, with phases that remain constant, while the tactics behind them flexible according to local vulnerabilities, literacy patterns, governance systems, cultural expectations, and risk perceptions (e.g., the seismic imperative in Kadıköy, or the trust deficit in New Belgrade).

The result is a phased blueprint, as presented below, that is both coherent across countries and sensitive to local specificities, allowing technical renovation processes to unfold alongside a parallel, equally vital social process, i.e. the construction of durable acceptance.

Phase 1 - Understanding the social terrain through context mapping and diagnostics:

the initial phase consists of immersing the engagement team in the daily life of the district, assembling a nuanced understanding of vulnerabilities, aspirations, informal power relations and existing engagement cultures. In Setúbal, Zaragoza, Belgrade and Kadıköy, the initial barriers, i.e. institutional mistrust, limited awareness of renovation processes, linguistic complexity, or the primacy of seismic risk, can easily become entrenched resistance if not addressed early. For this reason, the process takes inspiration from the hands-on methods implemented in the three SUPERSHINE lighthouses, where local facilitators conducted door-to-door visits, used translated materials, and organised micro-neighbourhood encounters to reach residents who would otherwise remain invisible. This approach proved particularly effective in ensuring that even disengaged or vulnerable households were brought into the early engagement perimeter.

Translating this into the fellow cities means tailoring the atmosphere of preparation to local dynamics. In Setúbal, the first step may involve informal conversations in stairwells or shared courtyards, especially with women’s groups and neighbourhood volunteers who already serve as social anchors. In Zaragoza, where trust in public services is more

established, the process may take the form of single-topic assemblies held in intercultural centres, complemented by visual materials that make technical concepts immediately accessible. In Belgrade, early trust-building requires an intermediary layer, like neutral facilitators, NGOs or academic partners, who can help residents interpret the renovation programme without associating it too closely with contested public institutions. In Kadıköy, where seismic fear shapes every discussion on housing, trust emerges when engineers and residents share the same table, jointly discussing structural integrity before raising issues of comfort or energy use.

This phase also draws on a key lesson from the engagement pathway in the lighthouses, that is to say that participatory “kick-offs” only work when they are lived rather than staged. In Herning, for example, the launch event attracted far more people than expected because it was designed not as a formal presentation but as an open community gathering with multilingual support and parallel activities for different age groups. In the fellow cities, a similar neighbourhood day, perhaps centred on the theme of “taking care of our building”, could create the light, convivial atmosphere needed to activate local networks before entering the technical dimension of renovation.

Phase 2 - Building the engagement architecture and its narrative voice: once trust begins to take shape, the second phase constructs the communication and engagement architecture that will accompany the entire renovation process. This architecture is as much relational as it is logistical: it determines how residents will receive information, how often, in what formats, from whom, and with what tone. D1.4 illustrates how multimodal engagement, i.e. face-to-face meetings complemented by digital channels, visual materials, trilingual leaflets, and hands-on demonstrations, ensures inclusivity even in highly diverse communities.

In Setúbal, the architecture leans on embodied communication, with mediators delivering messages in multiple languages and explaining technical concepts through lived examples (“how insulation changes winter warmth,” not “thermal transmittance”). In Zaragoza, the communication framework can integrate municipal participation platforms with social-inclusion services, ensuring coherence across departments. In Belgrade, transparency becomes the foundation: residents need clear, simplified explanations of financial schemes, ESCO models, responsibilities and expected savings. In Kadıköy, the engagement narrative must continuously relate energy measures to structural integrity, transforming energy performance from a secondary concern into a complementary element of seismic resilience.

The architecture also incorporates structured cycles of sessions that begin with values and visions, move to technical options, and conclude with validated decisions. Likewise, the use of real-life exemplars, such as guided visits to success stories, is essential for making abstract transformations tangible.

Phase 3 - Co-creation, co-design, or co-decision, turning residents into co-authors of renovation: the third phase marks the shift from preparation to genuine co-creation, transforming residents into co-authors of renovation solutions. The co-creation ladder in SUPERSHINE moves beyond consultation, as it involves hands-on, iterative sessions where residents interact with drawings, materials, models, prototypes and cost scenarios. The lighthouses experience provides strong evidence that participation becomes deeper and more confident when design choices are broken down into specific themes, e.g., comfort, air quality, shading, façade materials, courtyard functions, accessibility routes, each addressed in a dedicated session.

In Setúbal, co-design thrives when linked to lived concerns: elders discuss circulation and mobility during works; women's groups focus on lighting and safety; youth explore ideas for outdoor spaces. In Zaragoza, co-design should be embedded within existing neighbourhood structures, bridging social programmes with technical planning. In Belgrade, it requires technical credibility: including engineers, auditors or independent specialists helps counteract mistrust and demonstrates procedural fairness. In Kadıköy, co-design must explicitly integrate seismic assessments, showing how insulation, ventilation and renewable options align with structural strengthening.

The engagement pathways in the lighthouses also highlight the power of micro-co-construction activities, where residents co-build small elements such as shared seating, planter boxes, or garden sheds. These actions align with tactical urbanism, as they are small-scale, low-cost and quick-to-deliver interventions that allow cities to test and improve shared spaces before making permanent changes. Beyond their practical value, these simple, tactile interventions generated disproportionate social impact: pride, belonging and a sense of collective authorship. In the fellow cities, such exercises could unlock engagement even among residents who feel disconnected from technical discourse.

Phase 4 - Continuous engagement during implementation of the renovation: the fourth phase is the “stress test” of the entire engagement model, considering that construction disrupts daily life, and trust built over months can evaporate in days if communication falters. Dust, noise, access restrictions, and unforeseen delays affect all residents, but especially elders, vulnerable households and people with disabilities, so, every week of works requires visible engagement, not occasional updates.

In Setúbal, this means door-to-door check-ins during critical construction phases and on-site staff who can explain why disruptions are occurring and how long they will last. In Zaragoza, where many elders navigate the district through social services, alignment between renovation teams and social workers ensures continuous support. In Belgrade, predictability is essential: frequent micro-updates through messaging apps or entrance noticeboards reduce the risk of mistrust re-emerging at every small deviation. In Kadıköy, residents must be reassured through structured, engineer-led walkthroughs showing how seismic reinforcements are executed, and how efficiency upgrades integrate with safety.

D1.4 offers concrete strategies that proved highly effective, meaning short-horizon meetings (weekly planning for residents, not monthly presentations), guided visits to renovated spaces, which demystify the process and reduce anxiety, and parallel community events, such as clean-up days or small co-maintenance initiatives, which help maintain cohesion despite disruption. In this phase, engagement becomes a form of collective care. Residents must feel accompanied, not abandoned, by the process.

Phase 5 - Consolidation, learning, and long-term empowerment for future ownership: the final phase is where acceptance matures into ownership. As works conclude, residents need to understand, appreciate and internalise the benefits of the transformation. The experience in the Lighthouse of Herning shows that hands-on training sessions on new technologies (from thermostats to ventilation systems to solar controls) achieved full participation when conducted in accessible language and in familiar community spaces. This reduces post-renovation anxiety and ensures that energy savings are fully realised.

In Setúbal, a phase like this would reinforce comfort gains and alleviate energy poverty concerns through practical demonstrations and household-level support. In Zaragoza, post-renovation engagement can be integrated within social-service structures, allowing long-term monitoring of comfort and affordability. In Belgrade, publishing audited financial and performance outcomes is essential for strengthening trust and building momentum for future renovations. In Kadıköy, narrating renovation outcomes through the dual lens of seismic safety and energy efficiency helps shift local perceptions on integrated modernisation.

The pathway in the three SUPERSHINE lighthouses also shows how revitalised outdoor spaces, co-designed and co-managed, foster daily use and local identity: building on this, the fellow cities can create ongoing Living Labs, community oversight committees, green custodians or safety-and-efficiency groups, ensuring that the participatory spirit continues beyond the renovation itself. In this last phase, the renovated building becomes not just a technical achievement, but a shared legacy.

8.2 Environmental and Economic Performance: LCA- and LCC-informed Renovation Routes

This section translates the findings into three LCA-informed Blueprint “routes”, and into concrete guidance for follower cities.

Deep envelope renovation of inefficient multi-family blocks

The comparison between the unrenovated ACTUR block (“Casona”) and the deeply renovated Emmeline blocks in Zaragoza shows that a comprehensive envelope package – external insulation (ETICS) on façades, reinforced roof insulation and full window replacement – significantly reduces life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions per m² over 50 years, even when the embodied impacts of the additional materials are included. A similar

pattern appears when comparing the current Kadıköy housing stock with the ACTUR baseline: inefficient concrete blocks in heating-dominated or mixed climates have high operational impacts, and envelope performance is a key driver.

For the Blueprint, this supports a deep envelope renovation route for follower cities with large stocks of 1960–1990 concrete multifamily blocks in Mediterranean and continental climates. In practical terms, the LCA suggests that:

- When baseline operational demands for space heating and/or cooling are high, and the buildings are expected to remain in use for at least 30–40 years, deep envelope renovation (continuous ETICS on façades, substantial roof insulation and replacement of leaky windows with high-performance units) should be treated as the default option, rather than an exceptional, “nice-to-have” measure.
- Under these conditions, deep envelope renovation reduces life-cycle GWP per m² by roughly a quarter compared to a “no renovation” scenario, while the additional embodied impacts of insulation and windows remain proportionally limited over the 50-year horizon.
- Follower cities that identify blocks similar to “Casona” (concrete structure, uninsulated double-leaf walls, single glazing, high heating demand) should therefore be guided by the Blueprint towards an “Emmeline-type” deep envelope package as the preferred pathway.

This “deep envelope route” is consistent with the climate-adapted strategies presented in Part 1, where fabric-first measures are prioritised in climates with significant heating (and cooling) needs.

Partial renovation of small terraced estates in mild climates

The Brejoeira case in Setúbal represents a different context: a small terraced estate in a milder Atlantic–Mediterranean climate, with very poor envelope performance but strong social constraints linked to energy poverty and limited budgets. Here, the renovation concept combines a partial SATE / ETICS on façades, a roof upgrade and solar thermal systems for domestic hot water. The LCA shows that this partial package achieves a substantial reduction in life-cycle GWP per m² compared to the initial situation, while requiring less material and financial input than a full deep renovation.

For the Blueprint, this suggests a targeted partial renovation route for small estates in mild climates. The LCA results imply that:

- Where budgets are tight and buildings are small, follower cities can prioritise a limited set of high-impact measures (the most exposed façades, roofs and DHW systems) instead of waiting for a comprehensive, and possibly unrealistic, deep renovation.

- A well-designed partial package can deliver a large share of the potential life-cycle GWP reduction at lower embodied impact and lower investment, making it especially suitable for programmes aimed at vulnerable households and energy poverty.
- Blueprint guidance for cities with “Brejoeira-like” typologies should therefore emphasise:
 - first, identifying the most exposed façades and roofs;
 - second, applying moderate insulation thicknesses and basic airtightness measures; and
 - third, adding simple solar thermal systems for DHW where feasible and maintainable.

This does not replace deep renovation in the long term, but provides a realistic, LCA-supported option that can be deployed earlier and at scale

Building renovation in district heating contexts

The Belgrade IMS block (Block 29 – AČ128) illustrates a third situation: a large prefabricated multi-family building connected to a predominantly fossil-based district heating system. Even when a deep envelope renovation package (additional external insulation, improved roof insulation, high-performance windows) is modelled, the LCA shows that life-cycle GWP per m² remains comparatively high, because operational impacts are dominated by the carbon intensity of the heat supply.

For the Blueprint, this has a straightforward implication for follower cities with similar district heating contexts:

- Building-level deep renovation is necessary but not sufficient to reach low life-cycle GHG levels; the decarbonisation of the heat supply (fuel switch, renewable integration, improved controls and metering) must be addressed in parallel.
- Blueprint pathways for such cities should explicitly combine:
 - a building package similar to the one proposed for Belgrade (envelope and windows), and
 - a system-level component targeting the heat source and network performance.

For follower cities, the practical consequence is that projects on DH-connected buildings should not be planned in isolation. Whenever a city identifies “Block-29-like” buildings in its stock, the Blueprint should guide them to: (i) apply a deep envelope package at building scale, and simultaneously (ii) coordinate with utilities and energy planners to ensure that district-heating decarbonisation measures are scheduled and implemented in parallel. Only this combined route addresses the dominant life-cycle hotspots revealed by the LCA and aligns building-level renovation with long-term climate-neutrality goals.

To translate these outcomes into concrete guidance, the Blueprint should encourage each follower city to:

1. Map its stock against the demo typologies

- Classify local buildings as similar to “Casona/Emmeline-type blocks”, “Brejoeira-type terraced houses”, “Belgrade-type DH-fed blocks” or “Kadıköy-type multi-family groups”, based on structure, age, climate and energy system.

2. Select the corresponding LCA-informed pathway

- For each typology, choose between a deep envelope pathway, a targeted partial pathway or a combined building–system pathway, using the LCA results as evidence of which package delivers the largest life-cycle GHG reduction per m² over the 50-year horizon.

3. Use LCA ranges as decision-support, not as rigid targets

- Treat the numerical results (e.g. approximate GHG emissions per m² under each scenario) as indicative ranges that help rank options and communicate expected benefits, rather than as precise forecasts.

By embedding these typology- and climate-specific messages directly into the Blueprint pathways, the LCA results move from being a “background analysis” to acting as an operational decision-support tool: they help follower cities decide what kind of renovation package to apply, where, and with what level of ambition, in line with the overarching logic set out in Part 1.

While LCA supports the selection of renovation routes based on environmental performance, LCC provides a complementary economic lens, helping cities prioritise building typologies and intervention scales that deliver the highest value for money.

The aggregated indicators highlight several structural differences across the pilots:

- **High-density multifamily buildings**, such as Zaragoza’s ACTUR blocks, exhibit the lowest cost intensity per square metre, reflecting strong economies of scale and the high effectiveness of deep envelope renovation packages.
- **Small terraced estates in mild climates**, such as Setúbal’s Brejoeira neighbourhood, achieve substantial operational savings relative to their investment volume, demonstrating that targeted envelope upgrades can be economically favourable in contexts with limited budgets or energy-poverty considerations.
- **Large, dispersed building ensembles with fragmented renovation actions**, such as Kadıköy, show high cost intensity and limited operational improvements, indicating that isolated measures are insufficient and that coordinated block-level or district-level renovation strategies are required.

Together, these patterns reinforce the importance of aligning building typology, renovation depth, and local energy-system characteristics to ensure economically and environmentally efficient long-term transitions. They also demonstrate how LCC can serve as an operational decision-support tool for follower cities when integrated with LCA and energy performance assessments.

8.3 Summary Guide on Policy, Finance and Organizational Capacity

While each of the countries for the Fellow Cities have unique challenges, as discussed in previous sections of this report, their common goals (decarbonization, NZEB, deep renovation) allow for a shared set of high-impact policy levers that can accelerate the energy transition in the social housing sectors across the whole group.

8.3.1 Financial Mobilization and Blended Finance

- **Create National Decarbonization Funds:** Establish dedicated, revolving funds (or leverage existing ones like the RRF/EEF) that de-risk private capital through public guarantees, specifically targeting the social and multi-family housing sectors.
- **Scale Blended Finance:** Combine grants (for low-income/social housing), concessional loans (for public housing authorities/municipalities), and tax incentives (for owner-occupier social housing) to overcome the high upfront cost barrier.
- **Performance-Based Incentives:** Shift incentives from supporting a specific technology (e.g., insulation) to rewarding achieved energy savings (e.g., savings), ensuring a focus on deep renovation (NZEB-ready).

8.3.2 Administrative and Technical Capacity

- **Establish One-Stop Shops (OSS):** Centralized, regional, or municipal offices that provide technical assistance, manage grant applications, coordinate construction, and guide homeowners/housing associations through the entire renovation process. This is critical for simplifying the complex process, especially in multi-owner buildings (Spain, Serbia).
- **Certification and Skill Building:** Create a national certification for "Green Retrofit Managers" and heavily subsidize vocational training programs in the construction sector focused on high-efficiency installation techniques and Renewable Energy Sources (RES) integration.

8.3.3 Regulatory and Enforcement Levers

- **Mandatory Linkage of Upgrades:** For countries facing multiple structural issues (e.g., Türkiye's seismic risk, Serbia's boiler issues), mandate the integration of energy efficiency upgrades with other required structural or maintenance works to avoid "missed opportunities."
- **Performance Benchmarking:** Introduce strict, mandatory Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) for the social housing stock, coupled with a phased "Phase-Out/Renovation Deadline" for the worst-performing buildings (e.g., the bottom 15% of the housing stock).
- **Standardize Contracts:** Use public procurement power to standardize "Energy Performance Contracts" for multi-family/social housing, shifting the financial risk and performance guarantee to an Energy Service Company (ESCO).

8.3.4 RES and System Integration

- **Mandate On-site Renewables:** Require the integration of on-site RES (especially solar PV/thermal) in all deep renovation projects for multi-family social housing, potentially supporting community or collective self-consumption models.
- **Phase Out Fossil Fuels:** Implement policies and subsidies to rapidly phase out the most polluting and inefficient fossil fuel and solid-fuel heating systems (e.g., old coal/wood boilers in Serbia) in favor of high-efficiency heat pumps or connection to efficient district heating/cooling networks.

More 'lumped' policy and financial suggestions are as follows for the EU and non-EU Fellow Cities;

For Portugal & Spain (EU Members, RRF Access)

- **Mandate the "All-Inclusive" Model:** Focus on the All-Inclusive/Development archetype for RRF-funded social housing retrofits. This ensures that the deep renovation targets are met and that the complex bureaucratic process (grants, tax deductions) is entirely managed for the housing association or low-income owner.
- **Digital Integration:** Develop a standardized national digital platform (similar to a "digital building passport") that integrates with the OSS service, allowing for remote initial assessment, tracking of subsidy applications and performance monitoring post-renovation. This enhances efficiency and data collection.

For Serbia & Türkiye (Developing Systems, Financing Gaps)

- **Prioritize Institutional Linkage (Serbia):** The OSS must act as the primary coordinating entity between the Ministry of Mining and Energy (for fuel switching/boilers), the Ministry of Construction (for thermal integrity), and Local Self-

Government Units (for maintenance enforcement). The OSS is the operational arm of the inter-ministerial strategy.

- Integrate Seismic/Energy (Türkiye): The OSS should be the sole service provider for the "Dual Retrofit Grant/Loan". It must contain specialized technical staff capable of designing solutions that simultaneously address structural safety and energy performance, thereby maximizing the use of limited financial resources.
- Establish a Permanent Local Presence: Given the reliance on local engagement, the OSS should adopt a hybrid physical and digital model, providing accessible, localized physical service centers in high-density social housing areas to build community trust and handle paper-based

Together, the social engagement pathway, the LCA- and LCC-informed renovation routes and the financial, policy and organisational enablers form an integrated replication framework. This framework allows follower cities to move step by step from social readiness, through evidence-based technical choices, to the institutional conditions required for large-scale implementation.

9. Conclusion

A comparison of the four SUPERSHINE fellow cities reveals striking similarities in terms of structural vulnerabilities, governance limitations and social fragmentation, yet also notable differences in institutional capacity, cultural attitudes and the maturity of participatory practices. While all four contexts share the challenge of ageing building stocks and the need for energy-efficiency improvements, the social conditions that influence acceptance, engagement and co-creation vary significantly, shaping the feasibility and effectiveness of deep renovations at district scale.

Given the framework setting policy, technology and financial evaluation pillars elaborated by the SUPERSHINE Project, learnings from the Lighthouse Cities and analyses with less comprehensive data from the Fellow Cities, the present Task produced, on top of the these categories, methodologies and guidelines for the Fellow Cities that included LCA/LCC and SCLA assessments for the Fellow Cities which can be utilized by any aspiring city or municipality.

The SUPERSHINE model demonstrated in thorough studies of all its cities, that social acceptance is neither automatic nor static, as it develops when institutions listen with humility, when technical information is articulated without condescension, when design visibly incorporate residents' lived realities, and when renovation becomes a shared journey instead of a top-down mandate. Across the adaptation to Setúbal, Zaragoza, Belgrade and Kadıköy, the blueprint shows that acceptance is nurtured not through persuasion, but through relationships, not through slogans, but through consistent, reciprocal acts of presence.

The five-phase pathway detailed in previous sections and given the right technical and financial contingencies have been taken care of, reveals that engagement is cumulative: early trust-building opens the door to credible participation; transparent communication builds comprehension and reduces anxiety; co-design redistributes agency; accompaniment during construction preserves confidence in moments of disruption; and post-renovation continuity transforms temporary acceptance into long-term stewardship. These phases do not form a rigid sequence but rather a flexible ecosystem that must be attuned to local vulnerabilities, social composition and governance cultures.

What turns this blueprint into a replicable model is the concrete evidence produced by the three SUPERSHINE lighthouse pathways, i.e. Trieste, Riga and Herring. Their experience form the practical backbone of the model: a living laboratory showing how methods evolve, adapt and refine themselves when confronted with real communities, real buildings and real social and financial constraints.

In Trieste, engagement succeeded because the team invested in slow, patient relational work. Community walks, visits, micro-meetings in stairwells and conversations held in

shared courtyards made it possible to reach residents who rarely participate in institutional processes, including elders, migrant families and economically fragile households. The Trieste pathway demonstrated that early trust-building must be embedded in the everyday life of a neighbourhood, not performed from outside it. For replication purposes, this means that cities should not start with assemblies or formal workshops, but with proximity-based encounters that treat residents as partners rather than beneficiaries.

In Riga, where multilingualism, ethnic diversity and varying levels of digital literacy intersect, engagement practices relied heavily on translation, not only linguistic but conceptual: visual materials, simplified diagrams of energy flows, and interactive discussions replaced technical presentations and ensured that even residents with limited literacy could meaningfully participate. Riga also pioneered hybrid engagement, combining digital tools with in-person sessions to avoid excluding older residents or those without internet access. Its experience demonstrates that replicability requires taking literacy and accessibility seriously: a city cannot ask residents to engage with plans they cannot fully understand.

In Herning, the lighthouse pathway showed the power of embodied engagement and shared decision-making. Community-building micro-actions, such as small co-construction activities, participatory mapping of comfort hotspots, or joint preparation for outdoor rewilding, proved far more effective than conventional consultation. Herning illustrated that when residents physically shape part of the environment, even in small ways, their sense of ownership increases and acceptance rises accordingly. This embodied approach is highly transferable: Setúbal may use it to activate youth and women's groups; Zaragoza could integrate it into its cultural centres; Belgrade could engage its technically skilled residents in participatory audits; and Kadıköy could link it to seismic-awareness demonstrations.

The lighthouse pathways also make clear that the construction preparation phase must be treated as a critical engagement moment: Trieste's weekly micro-updates, Riga's WhatsApp groups for rapid schedule clarification, and Herning's guided visits to already-renovated buildings all demonstrated that predictable, proximity-based communication prevents frustration and sustains trust. These practices are simple, inexpensive and directly replicable in all four fellow cities.

Finally, post-renovation, the lighthouses showed that acceptance becomes durable only when residents feel equipped to use and care for the improvements. Training on energy interfaces in Riga, participatory monitoring of comfort in Herning, and the creation of small stewardship groups in Trieste all transformed renovated spaces into community assets. These practices point towards a replicability principle: renovation must end not with handover, but with a new cycle of shared responsibility.

Together, the blueprint and the lighthouse pathways show that engagement is not decorative, but, instead, structural: when residents see their input reflected in design decisions, when they receive honest explanations during disruptions, and when they

understand and value the improvements made to their homes, acceptance shifts from fragile to enduring.

As a general consideration, it must be noted that replication cannot be achieved through technical and financial templates, no matter how good and suitable they are, as it demands sensitivity to the history of each place, attention to inequalities, and the willingness to reinterpret proven practices in ways that resonate locally. Yet, across Setúbal, Zaragoza, Belgrade and Kadıköy, a constant emerges, that is to say when residents feel respected, informed and visible, renovation becomes not merely acceptable, but technically, socially and culturally transformative.

The SUPERSHINE journey demonstrates clearly that the Blueprint for other European cities can be roughly distilled into three core pillars: Integration, Inclusivity, and Institutional Trust.

- **Integration:** Successful cities treat energy renovation as a holistic urban renewal project, linking energy performance, thermal comfort with local imperatives such as seismic safety, accessibility, and green infrastructure.
- **Inclusivity:** Policies must move beyond "consultation" toward "co-creation," empowering residents—particularly those in energy poverty—to help shape the transformation of their neighbourhoods.
- **Institutional Trust:** Transparent financial flows, clear performance guarantees, and localized mediation are essential to mobilize the "investment culture" needed for long-term sustainability.

Ultimately, affordable social housing initiatives have the potential to be the vanguard of Europe's climate goals. By adopting this integrated approach, cities can ensure that the energy transition is not just a technical upgrade, but a powerful engine for social inclusion, health, and urban resilience. The path forward is clear, once the community is seamlessly involved, the transition becomes not only feasible but inevitable.

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D5.3 Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities- Part 2

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ANNEX I Definitions of LCC Indicators

Nominal Life Cycle Cost (LCC)

The nominal Life Cycle Cost represents the cumulative sum of all costs incurred over the 50-year analysis period, expressed in nominal terms. It includes initial investment costs (CAPEX), operational and maintenance costs (OPEX), replacement costs, and accounts for residual values where applicable. This indicator provides an overall measure of the total economic effort associated with the renovation technologies over their life cycle.

Net Present Cost (NPC)

The Net Present Cost expresses the total life-cycle cost discounted to the reference year. By applying a discount rate, costs occurring at different points in time are converted into present-value terms, allowing a consistent economic evaluation over the analysis period. NPC is a central indicator in life-cycle economic assessments, as it reflects the time value of money and supports the interpretation of long-term investment-related impacts.

Equivalent Annual Cost (EAC)

The Equivalent Annual Cost converts the Net Present Cost into a uniform annual value over the 50-year reference period. This indicator expresses the life-cycle cost as an average annual cost, facilitating interpretation and comparison across renovation solutions and pilot cases with different cost profiles. EAC is particularly useful for communicating long-term affordability and economic implications.

Normalised Indicators per Functional Unit

To support comparability across buildings of different sizes, typologies, and contexts, selected KPIs are also expressed per functional unit, defined as one square metre of heated floor area (m²).

Life Cycle Cost per Functional Unit (LCC per m²)

This indicator represents the nominal life-cycle cost normalised by the heated floor area, enabling scale-independent comparison between pilot cases and renovation technologies.

Net Present Cost per Functional Unit (NPC per m²)

The NPC per m² expresses the discounted life-cycle cost per square metre, allowing comparison of economic performance across different buildings and geographical contexts.

Equivalent Annual Cost per Functional Unit (EAC per m²)

The EAC per m² represents the average annual cost per square metre over the analysis period. This indicator supports spatial interpretation of long-term costs and is commonly used in building economics and housing policy analyses.

Operational Expenditure per Functional Unit (OPEX per m²)

Operational expenditure per m² captures the annual operating costs associated with the renovated buildings, with a particular focus on energy-related costs. This indicator highlights the contribution of the implemented renovation technologies to reducing ongoing costs during the use phase and provides a direct link to the analysis of operational cost savings presented in the subsequent sections.

Rationale for KPI Selection

The selected KPIs provide a robust and transparent representation of life-cycle economic performance while remaining feasible within the constraints of available data. More advanced financial indicators, such as internal rates of return or detailed stakeholder-specific cost allocations, were not included due to data limitations and the heterogeneity of pilot contexts. The adopted indicators therefore prioritise comparability, clarity, and methodological consistency, ensuring that the LCC results effectively support the assessment of the economic implications of SUPERSHINE renovation technologies.